

Pejorative and Productive?

The legacy of Finlandization at home and abroad

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Abstract

In the past few years Finlandization has been a hot topic in both domestic Finnish politics, with its accession to NATO, and internationally, in the case of Ukraine. This paper analyzes how the term has been applied to both contexts and how it will continue to be relevant in the future. Through an analysis of Finland's practical actions with Western organizations and countries, the paper finds that claims of Finlandization continuing following the end of the Cold War are instead just part of the historical balancing act in Finnish foreign policy, one that is now oriented towards the U.S., and not completely a continuation of Kekkonen-style Finlandization. Additionally, the paper addresses the infatuation of international policy-makers to suggest the Soviet-era "Finnish model," and instead suggests post-1992 actions as a more applicable example. The paper builds upon the work of Weislander (2022), Arter (2023), and Juntunen (2017), among others.

Introduction

In recent years, Finland's geopolitical policy has changed dramatically, most notably with its 2023 accession to NATO. This has sparked a discussion on just how Finland has managed to get to this position, a far cry from the censored, isolated period of Finlandization during the Cold War. It is here that the conversation on Finlandization has been revitalized; somehow both about how it is a model for other nations to follow, but also an unfavorable position that Finland managed to escape.

This paper challenges two separate commonly held assumptions. The first assumption is that Finlandization is over. I argue that it hasn't yet ended completely, it has just reoriented itself towards another state: the U.S.. Informed by its long history with Russia and the USSR, Finland's near misses with loss of sovereignty has built a "subconscious" that reacts when appeasement and conciliation are used at the foreign policy table. The second assumption is that Finlandization is a lesson to learn from. I argue, like many others before me, that Finlandization is too unique a concept to model after, informed by centuries of specific events and geographical context. What I propose is that one should look to the post-Cold War period instead, using how Finland changed from a heavily censored and suppressed country, to one that is considered a strong democracy and deeply integrated within NATO.

In *Chapter 1: Finlandization as History* I outline key historical events and conduct a literature review around the topic of Finlandization, with the rest of my paper exploring how the concept has evolved. In *Chapter 2: Finlandization as a Continuation of History* I discuss to what extent and form Finlandization exists in current-day Finland with an evaluation against Arter's (2022) concept of post-Finlandization, and in *Chapter 3: Finlandization as an Export* I take a look at what of Finlandization, if anything, is applicable to other nations.

Chapter 1: Finlandization as History

What is Finlandization?

Finlandization as a topic has been thoroughly explored by academics, with the term being coined in 1961 by West German political scientist Richard Lowenthal. However, that doesn't mean that there is a standardized or widely accepted definition. Finlandization as a concept is rooted deeply in Finland's history. While many definitions will simplify the concept to "a fear of a larger neighbor," there is additional nuance and reasoning behind Finland's approach than just that. Otherwise, why use Finlandization and not something more broadly understood like "neutrality" (as is done with Sweden)?

Finlandization refers to Finland's policy of deference and neutrality towards Russia during the Cold War, informed by WWII era conflicts and centuries of being a subject under the Swedish and Russian empires. This history of being between balanced between east and west will play out throughout the entire paper. While there exists other definitions as well, for this paper, unless otherwise stated, I will use a descriptive definition where Finlandization is a neutral term to describe the voluntary relationship of a smaller power creating stability through reassuring a larger power with neutrality.

To provide some context into this relationship, I will attempt to briefly explain the various stages of Finland from pre-independence, to the current day situation. Much of the information comes from Lavery's (2006) book, "The History of Finland," supplemented by my own knowledge and other sources.

History

Pre-independence

Finland as we know it today didn't exist as even a concept until the 19th century. Instead, it began as a sparsely populated and barely developed area situated between the Kingdom of Sweden

to the west, and the Novgorod Republic to the east. It wasn't until 1100s that Sweden began to express interest in the area as a means to compete with the powerful Novgorod Republic.

The land was slowly taken over by Sweden through various crusades, and incorporated into the kingdom over the next 800 years. The conflict between Sweden and the various Russia powers that began in the 12th century continued throughout this period, with the control over the Baltic sea being a common theme. This culminated in the Finnish War during the Napoleonic Wars (1803-1815) which ended with a Swedish loss in 1809, handing much of its eastern territory over to Russia to form the autonomous Grand Duchy of Finland.

Under Russia, the concept of the Finnish nation began to develop. Swept up in the wave of nationalism that was spreading across the European mainland, citizens of the Grand Duchy developed an origin mythology in the *Kalevala*¹, sparked a debate over the working-class Finnish language, and defined their shared culture. And thus from people with no previously shared common identity, a fierce idea of Finland began to grow.

In a timely turn of events, during the late 19th century the Russian leadership under Tsar Alexander III began to tighten the leash around the Grand Duchy, only spurring further support for this idea of an independent Finland. Autonomy was greatly reduced; the Russian language was enforced, Finland's army was merged with Russia, economic ties were tightened, and most importantly, the legislative process was now required to go through that of Russia's. So when Russia had issues of its own during the Communist October Revolution, the Finnish government took action. It was within this small window of time that Finland submitted its formal declaration of independence. The declaration was passed in parliament and presented to the new Bolshevik government in Moscow, who preoccupied with revolution and hoping that Finns would join, accepted the independence without any condition. Finland thus became a sovereign nation on December 6th, 1917.

¹ The national epic of Finland; a creation myth like that of Greek mythology, and a culturally defining work like *Beowulf*.

WWII-era conflicts

The interwar period was rife with conflict for Finland, who was reeling from the aftereffects of a civil war between the Red socialist and White liberal factions that was spurred on by the October Revolution in Russia. The Whites, supported by Imperial Germany, won the war but continued to struggle in managing outside influence from the neighboring Soviet Union. The fear of a Soviet-sponsored uprising was high, with a majority of Finns wary of any communist or socialist tendencies.

Figure 1: Map of the Winter War by Robert M. Citino (2014)

This conflict culminated in a Soviet invasion of Finland in 1939, with a goal of expanding the buffer around the exposed Leningrad.² The Finns managed to hold on for a few months, but the Soviets broke through the Karelian Isthmus and pushed forward. However, both sides were getting

² Leningrad was just about 30 miles away from the Finnish border at the time.

fatigued and agreed to a peace deal, with Finland ceding nine percent of its territory: more than Soviet pre-war demands.

When Nazi Germany initiated Operation Barbarossa in 1941, Finland believed it had a chance to retake territory that it had previously lost. Finland drew on ties that it developed during the Civil War to begin a counter-offensive against the USSR, now allied with Nazi Germany. In the ensuing Continuation War, Finland managed to take some ground, but the gains were lost after the Soviets pushed back from Leningrad. Finland eventually capitulated, forming the borders that we know today.

Post-WWII and Cold War

Following the end of WWII, there was a shift in the underlying understanding between Finland and the USSR. While still threatening, Finland's territorial sovereignty was no longer threatened. This was in great contrast with before, where a complete takeover was never out of the picture. This threat was replaced by closer ties, both politically and economically. Economically, Finland was forced to pay reparations in the form of both cash and materiel, reparations that made the Finnish economy inseparable from the USSR's. Politically, Finland was forced to sign the *Ystävyyss-, yhteistyö- ja avunantosopimus* or Agreement of Friendship, Cooperation, and Mutual Assistance of 1948 (YYA/FCMA Treaty), embedding Soviet interests with Finnish ones. While it guaranteed Finland's neutrality, the treaty made it so that Finland couldn't do anything that endangered the Soviet's interests and essentially gave the USSR a say over much of Finnish domestic politics; setting the context for Finland's solitude. It was during this period that Finland was completely alone, with no outside support, not wanting to even be seen as contradicting the YYA-treaty.

The relationship became tied together further with the Presidency of Urho Kekkonen. Kekkonen became the means which the USSR interfaced with Finland, the only person that they decided they could trust. To gain any favor with the government meant having to follow Kekkonen. If not, you would be seen as unfavorable in the eyes of the USSR. Such was the case with the Note Crisis of 1961. Under his leadership, Finland went through multiple crises caused by the Soviet

Union, crises in which their influence directly changed the course of domestic politics and to some, sovereignty, in Finland. With the Note Crisis, Soviet leaders were dissatisfied with the makeup of the Finnish parliament, worried that they would back Kekkonen's opponent in the 1962 election. Thus, they threatened to break Finland's neutrality and begin security negotiations. When Kekkonen managed to "handle" the situation to maintain neutrality, he in the process regained the support of Finnish politicians and disbanded the parliament for a more favorable one. And such was the biggest criticism of his nearly 26 year presidential administration. Finland became subservient to Russia, self- and regular censorship rampant with politicians carefully watching their words, and the words of their citizens. Power shifted towards the role of the president and away from the people. This was so much an issue that after Kekkonen, the Finnish parliament placed restrictions on the role of president, limiting terms to two six year terms, requiring a popular vote, and significantly lowering their powers.

In the few years between Kekkonen's presidency and the fall of the Soviet Union, President Mauno Koivisto maintained a friendly relationship with the USSR, but more distant and moderate than that of Kekkonen.

Post-Cold War

Following the end of the Cold War, Finland officially ended its policy of neutrality, replacing it instead with a policy of military non-alignment. What it means is that while Finland will no longer be completely isolated, it will still not commit to any binding military alliances. While maintaining this military non-alliance, Finland slowly integrated structurally into the West. Although Finland was ideologically and culturally closer to the West than the East, it was only in the post-Cold War situation that they formalized these ties. First by increasing military cooperation and interoperability with NATO through the Partnership for Peace (PfP) in 1994, joining the EU in 1995, and the Eurozone in 1999, among others.

However, this all changed in 2022 with the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Suddenly, Finland and Sweden both decided to ditch their non-aligned policy and join NATO. And thus to many, the era of

Finlandization officially ended. Finland put any semblance of neutrality behind and joined a military alliance; *Ei koskaan enää yksin*, never again alone.³

Literature Review

Finlandization has many forms, more than just the policy of deference and neutrality towards Russia that was explained at the beginning of this chapter. Here I will explore how academic literature has discussed this issue, with a focus on its definition, its ongoing effects, and its current-day legacy.

Defining Finlandization and Neutrality

Given that Finlandization has so many definitions, it is important to understand what it means when the term is referenced. Does it mean just neutrality? Does it mean deference? Does it mean empowerment? Or does it mean something else? The three articles that helped most in shaping my understanding of Finlandization are Arter (2023), Forsberg and Pesu (2016), and Juntunen (2017).

Forsberg and Pesu (2016) describe the different ways people have used the term, from “a policy of voluntarily accommodating interests and restricting sovereignty to preserve the independence of a country and avoid causing political tensions with a more powerful neighbouring country,” to “political remote control from abroad,” or as “a pseudo-morphism—a political culture that embraced the ideals, conventions, and principles of totalitarianism without being totalitarian.”⁴

Arter (2023) succinctly sums up Finlandization as a distinctly Finnish phenomenon, one that has two possible meanings. In Finnish there are two words that would translate to “Finlandization” in English: *suomettuminen* and *suomettaminen*. These similar but different terms change the perspective in which the phenomenon can be understood. The first means “a pro-active large power strategy designed to influence the politics of a small neighbouring state”, and the second is “a form of preventative diplomacy practised by a small state, concerned to anticipate an adverse reaction on

³ A quote by General Adolf Ehrnrooth after the Winter War.

⁴ “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland: The Ideal Type, the Historical Model, and the Lessons Learnt,” *Diplomacy & Statecraft* 27, no. 3 (July 2, 2016): 476, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592296.2016.1196069>.

the part of a large-power neighbour and in this way preserve its independence and sovereignty.”⁵ He then gives it four features that uniquely shape its context: (i) political geography; (ii) treaty obligation; (iii) constitutional prescription; (iv) party system dynamics.⁶ Within Finland, these terms are usually interpreted as pejorative, as Juntunen (2017) and Forsberg and Pesu (2016) explain. This negative image of Finland in the West began with the 1958 *yöpakkaskriisi* or Night Frost Crisis and the 1961 *noottikriisi* or Note Crisis, who saw these events as warnings of what close relations with the Soviet Union could cause.⁷ Juntunen explains that this term has since been used to criticize flaws in Finnish actions, often portraying Finnish leaders as weak or conciliatory.⁸

While it doesn't explicitly explain these features as being unique to Finlandization, Forsberg and Pesu (2016) do cover each of them in their article. They ultimately describe Finlandization as a means of pursuing its own national interests through *realpolitik*, “not simply a policy of limitless accommodation . . . [but also] not a policy that would have led to radical gains.”⁹ They do concede that some actions by Finland in regard to the USSR were “clearly excessive”, but “were in-built in the structures of Finlandisation as a political culture.”¹⁰

Professor Lavery in his interview with me highlights this “political culture” as a willing choice. He argues that Finland wasn't less of a democracy than other European countries as Finns chose to place those limitations there. Lavery says Finlandization is a “excessive use of foreign policy,” one that directs the domestic policy. The reason he gives for this policy was that Finland was completely alone in terms of facing the Soviet Union and grew to build this culture of deference as a means building positive relations with their neighbor to the east.¹¹

Juntunen (2017) has two additional interpretations of Finlandization: descriptive and emancipatory. The descriptive meaning is a neutral term to describe the voluntary relationship of a

⁵ David Arter, “From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation? Finland's Road to a NATO Application,” *European Security* 32, no. 2 (April 3, 2023): 172, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839.2022.2113062>.

⁶ Arter, 173.

⁷ “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 475.

⁸ “Helsinki Syndrome: The Parachronistic Renaissance of Finlandization in International Politics,” *New Perspectives* 25, no. 1 (February 1, 2017): 66, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2336825X1702500103>.

⁹ “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 488.

¹⁰ 490.

¹¹ Jason Lavery, “Finlandization: Interview with Jason Lavery” (By AnThu Nguyen, December 13, 2024).

smaller power creating stability through reassuring a larger power with neutrality. The emancipatory meaning is a revisionary term used by other Soviet bloc nations during the cold war, describing a smaller power taking initiative to neutralize the threat of a larger power without giving in.¹² These two meanings of Finlandization show just how complex a topic it is. In total, these are the four definitions outlined:

1. Descriptive: a neutral term to describe the voluntary relationship of a smaller power creating stability through reassuring a larger power with neutrality
2. Pejorative (international): *suomettuminen*, a larger power forcing a smaller one into neutrality
3. Pejorative (domestic): *suomettaminen*, a smaller power capitulating to a larger power to maintain sovereignty
4. Emancipatory: a smaller power taking initiative to neutralize the threat of a larger power without giving in (used by Soviet states in the 80s)¹³

As stated earlier, for this paper, I will be referring to Finlandization through the descriptive meaning, unless otherwise stated.

Many authors explicitly refer to Finlandization as a realist policy. Kivimäki (2015) describes Finlandization as an approach that “relies on a geopolitical interpretation of realism,” one that “focuses on states, considers power resources as central to world politics, and relates them on the one hand to the interest of nations to remain sovereign, and on the other to the big power competition for prominence and relative position in world politics.”¹⁴ Frazén (2023) agrees, “a policy based on survival by maintaining sovereignty while avoiding confrontation with a more powerful neighbour.”¹⁵ More on this in *Finlandization as a Framework*.

Additionally, the term neutrality itself also has multiple possible meanings. Pakkasvirta and Tuominen (2024) discuss this in their article, explaining how it originally was a legal term, referring to a state’s non-participation in war. After WWII, the term came to mean non-participation in any international conflict. Now, they assert, neutrality means non-participation in military alliances.

¹² Juntunen, “Helsinki Syndrome,” 65.

¹³ Juntunen, “Helsinki Syndrome.”

¹⁴ “Finlandization and the Peaceful Development of China,” *The Chinese Journal of International Politics* 8, no. 2 (2015): 141, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48615925>.

¹⁵ “A Qualitative Case Study of Finland’s and Sweden’s NATO Applications: Analysing the Case Through Liberalism and Neorealism” (Malmö University, 2023), 11, <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:mau:diva-62159>.

They trace this change in Finland as it followed each evolution of “neutrality,” into the formally “non-aligned” position they take today.¹⁶ Other authors like Arter (2023), Aunesluoma and Rainio-Niemi (2016), and more also recognize this change, using it to explain how an identity of neutrality and Finlandization persists. Concepts of neutrality and non-alignment in regards to Sweden are explored by Weislander (2022), whose framework forms the basis for *Chapter 2: Finlandization as a Continuation of History*.

Origins and Effects of Finlandization (Pre-1992)

Regardless of the definition of Finlandization, all sources recognize that it had a tangible effect of some kind on Finnish actions. Even in the sources that describe it as a façade, they acknowledge it had effects of some kind. This is key in understanding any modern day effects of Finlandization as it is rooted in these historical experiences and understandings.

Virkki (2023) describes Finlandization as a tree: rooted in the historical power dynamics of the Baltic Sea, green leaves made up of Soviet reconnaissance, and the most visible flowers being Finnish leadership’s silence on and praise of its neighbor. This tree grew out of Finland’s experience following WWII: being forced to sign the YYA-treaty, and the ongoing fear of Communist revolution known as *Vaaran vuodet* or “The Years of Danger”.¹⁷ This treaty would go on to shape all of Finland’s interactions with the USSR.¹⁸

Arter (2023) describes this as the “dark ages of Finlandization,” where there were two forms of ongoing self-censorship as a result of overwhelming Soviet influence: passive and active self-censorship. Passive self-censorship was the avoidance of criticism of the USSR out of genuine fear. Active, in comparison, was deliberate self-regulation in order for political gains in Soviet eyes, something that Nevakivi (1996) identifies as uniquely Finnish: a “decaying elite culture.”¹⁹ This censorship covered films, music, and textbooks, omitting negative depictions or criticism of the

¹⁶ “From Cold War ‘Neutrality’ to the West: Finland’s Route to the European Union and NATO,” in *Neutrality After 1989: New Paths in the Post-Cold War World* (E-International Relations, 2024), 48.

¹⁷ *Jälkisuomettumisen ruumiinavaus*, 1st ed., 2023, chap. 2, <https://www.ellibs.com/fi/book/9789523825529>.

¹⁸ Forsberg and Pesu, “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 478.

¹⁹ *Miten Kekkonen pääsi valtaan ja Suomi suomettui* (Helsingissä : Otava, 1996); quoted in, Arter, “From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation?” 175.

USSR.²⁰ What this led to, Arter argues, was an impossibility to distinguish between foreign and domestic policy.²¹ Forsberg and Pesu (2016) add that during this “worst era of Finlandisation,” Kekkonen played an important role in maintaining the relationship with the USSR, providing “flattering and talk of friendship, irrespective of the actual state of affairs,”²² but also guiding the country through the two aforementioned crises, “seal[ing] his position as a guarantor of good relations with the Soviet Union.”²³

Maude (1982) on the other hand, explains some of these actions as originating from Finnish culture and identity, as opposed to being fully cultivated by fears of the USSR. While he concedes that it has been reinforced by Soviet pressures, he argues a lack of criticism or comment on other countries in relation to the USSR originates from a Finnish tradition of authoritarianism, and a historical connection with Germany and not liberal Scandinavia. Thus Finns are sated with an okay relationship with Soviet Russia, and to others say “*mitä se kuuluu meille?*” or “what does it concern us?”²⁴

Medvedev (1999) describes Finlandization as a type of “neurosis” stemming from the 19th-century relationship with Russia, affecting the minds of Finns and distorting their behavior towards the USSR.²⁵ Juntunen (2017), while agreeing that past history plays a role, adds that it isn’t solely history that informed Finland’s actions, but also changes in East-West relations and intentional decisions made by Finnish elites.²⁶

Pakkasvirta and Tuominen (2024) describe two opposing approaches to this neutrality. The first, a realist explanation, focuses on the influence of structural and external factors: that being located between two opposing blocs. Small states can only do so much, so must “either join alliances or proclaim neutrality to survive.” The second, a constructivist/liberal explanation,

²⁰ YLE News, “Researcher: Communist Teaching Experiment Much Broader Than Thought” (News, May 6, 2016), <https://yle.fi/a/3-8861804>.

²¹ “From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation?” 175.

²² “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 480.

²³ 481.

²⁴ “The Further Shores of Finlandization,” *Cooperation and Conflict* 17, no. 1 (1982): 10, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/45083273>.

²⁵ Sergei Medvedev, “Russia as the Subconsciousness of Finland,” *Security Dialogue* 30, no. 1 (1999): 101, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44472168>.

²⁶ “Helsinki Syndrome,” 75.

highlighting international law, norms, and state identity: the Finnish identity of Nordicism helped push it to differentiate itself from “conflict-prone Europe,” using neutrality in the UN arena as one way of doing so.²⁷ Forsberg and Pesu (2016) argue that the approaches exist concurrently, with the relationship of realist versus liberal policy existing since the mid-19 century through the Hegelian Fennoman nationalist movement. They claim that friendly relations with Russia during the Cold War continued from this period, with Finland seeing positive relations as providing room for political maneuver.²⁸ My interview with Professor Lavery reflects much of this same sentiment.²⁹

A “Post-Finlandization”

Juntunen (2017) lists four definitions in his paper but Arter (2023) has built upon this with a new one: *jälkisuomettuminen*, or “post-Finlandization.” This term is the concept that sparked my research into this topic and is the primary focus of this paper.³⁰

Arter describes post-Finlandization as a continuation of Finlandization following the end of the Cold War: continuing effects even after the Soviet Union was gone. He describes four defining features of post-Finlandization as:

1. The persistence of a Cold War mentality, and the continued pursuit of Kekkonen-style preventative diplomacy, in Finland’s Baltic policy in the early 1990s.
2. A naïve belief in the prospects for successful democratisation and respect for human rights in the Russian Federation.
3. A reluctance to read and react to the signs of authoritarianism in the Russian Federation and the resurgence of post-imperialist aggression in Putin’s foreign policy.
4. An “official foreign policy” in EU Finland of military non-alignment coupled with a credible national defence that, in the manner of “dark age” Finlandisation, was not to be questioned.³¹

Arter’s definition lines up well with the effects of censorship, appeasement, and fear explained in Lavery (2006), Forsberg and Pesu (2016), and Medvedev (1999). This definition will be important as I will be using it to compare against my findings of Finnish integration to the West.

²⁷ “From Cold War ‘Neutrality’ to the West,” 39.

²⁸ “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 477.

²⁹ Lavery, “Finlandization Interview.”

³⁰ Arter, “From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation?”

³¹ Arter, 177.

Of primary concern to me however, is Arter's claim (as well as that of others) that Finlandization is over with Finland's accession to NATO. To understand whether or not effects continue to remain, I will explore the transformation of Finlandization over time, including this concept of "post-Finlandization".

Finlandization as a Framework

While many see NATO accession as the end of Finlandization, the Russian invasion of Ukraine has recently reignited discussion of Finlandization as a model for security abroad. One of the most high profile mentions was French President Emmanuel Macron saying Finlandization was "one of the models on the table."³² Others like Gilley (2010) suggest it be applied to Taiwan-China relations.³³ However, this is by no means a new idea. References to Finland as a "model" have been made since during the Cold War, often highlighting Finland's unusual success (or negative byproducts) in navigating its difficult relationship with the USSR. Such was the case when "the Finnish model" was proposed for Soviet states during the 80s as described by Juntunen (2017).³⁴

Others argue against applying Finlandization as a model, explaining that the Finnish case is uniquely different and doesn't apply elsewhere. Kallio (2010) directly responds to Gilley (2010), saying that Finland in the USSR's eyes was independent, whereas China doesn't recognize Taiwan. This, along with the fact that Finland had no other allies during the Cold War compared to Taiwan being under the U.S.'s military umbrella, and the USSR not opposing Finnish self-defense versus China being clearly opposed, makes Finlandization not applicable.³⁵ Scholars and politicians that take this position argue that using the model divorces the term from its original context and offers no benefit for the recipient nation.

³² Cora Engelbrecht, "'Finlandization' of Ukraine Is Part of the Diplomatic Discourse. But What Does That Mean?" *The New York Times: World*, February 8, 2022, <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/02/08/world/europe/ukraine-russia-finlandization.html>.

³³ "Not So Dire Straits: How the Finlandization of Taiwan Benefits U.S. Security," *Foreign Affairs* 89, no. 1 (2010): 44–60, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20699782>.

³⁴ Juntunen, "Helsinki Syndrome."

³⁵ "Finlandization Is No Model for Taiwan to Follow" (Finnish Institute of International Affairs, February 5, 2010), https://web.archive.org/web/20161024050111/http://www.fia.fi/en/blog/259/finlandization_is_no_model_for_taiwan_to_follow/.

In regards to Finlandization being used as a model, Juntunen (2017) argues that this “parachro-nistic” application of it in other contexts and time periods is an overgeneralization of history and is moot due to Finlandization’s “contextual prerequisites.”³⁶ He explains that the necessary preconditions for Cold War-era Finlandization developed in the decade after WWII. Unlike realist theory which argues that actions are determined through the logic of great power competition and international anarchy, Finlandization was uniquely constructed around the positive change from threatened sovereignty in the 1940s to an explicitly recognized independence in the 1950s, and also intentional decisions made by Finnish leaders.³⁷ Arter (2023) agrees directly with Juntunen (2017), saying that “Finlandisation should be set in its historic setting rather than simply viewed as a wider theory of ‘adaptive acquiescence’ practised by a small state in the lee of a large, powerful neighbour.”³⁸ He specifically points out the influence of seven centuries under Sweden and a century under the Tsarist Russian empire on Finnish political culture as differing from Ukraine.³⁹ Maude (1982) on the other hand identifies the YYA/FCMA Treaty as making the Finnish case unique: binding them to consider Soviet security needs, while at the same time providing enough flexibility to avoid implementation of the treaty.⁴⁰

The realist part of the conversation isn’t as developed in the literature but some exists. Betts (2015) explains this side succinctly when he says “Finlandization was a pejorative term. Realists, however, would see it as quite a good deal considering the alternative. Finland accepted a loss of independence in foreign policy but retained independence in its domestic political order, remaining a robust democracy. And what was the alternative?”⁴¹ In this he explains the crux of the realist perspective: that Finland as a small, threatened country had no option. Regardless of identity or history, the country took whatever action it could to survive. This is the standard position that many make of Finland in many of its historical events from the Finnish Civil War, the Winter Wars, and Finlandization; there was no other option. Kulali Martin (2024) agrees, explaining Finland’s neutral

³⁶ “Helsinki Syndrome” p. .

³⁷ 71, 75.

³⁸ “From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation?” 173.

³⁹ 172.

⁴⁰ “The Further Shores of Finlandization,” 6.

⁴¹ “The Realist Persuasion,” *The National Interest*, no. 139 (2015): 52, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44028493>.

policies as a “geopolitical necessity” and “realpolitik”.⁴²

While Lavery (2024) agrees with the perception of Finlandization as a realistic policy based on what would best neutralize Soviet aggression, he contends that the USSR only had a defensive interest in Finland. As long as Finland did not join any alliances or pose a threat as a vehicle of invasion, then the USSR would leave them alone. He explains that this perception continued after 1992, only shattering in 2022 once Russia invaded Ukraine.⁴³

Holmilla and Ahonen (2022) take a slightly different approach in making lessons. While not applying Finlandization as a concept in its entirety, they draw lessons from the idea to be applied to Ukraine. They draw three broader lessons from Finlandization: wartime achievements must be turned into political leverage and establish a future relationship, both east and west must be embraced for long-term survival, and an overly deferential domestic political situation must be avoided.⁴⁴ Whether or not these lessons are correct or not is not the point; Holmilla and Ahonen’s conclusions are the first on the topic of Finlandization I’ve seen that neither reject or embrace the model in full, but rather approach a middle ground of viewing it as a similar case study.

This debate is part of a larger one on whether or not historical factors are important in IR frameworks. Hobson and Lawson (2008) provide an overview of each different way of applying history, ranging from high generality (constructionism/neorealism) to low generality (deconstructionism/radical historicism).⁴⁵ They opine that both ends are insufficient, and one must use bits of both to adequately encapsulate a phenomenon in what they call historicist historical sociology. They take the generalization from “history without historicism”/neorealism and the contextualization from radical historicism and combine them in order to try to resolve some differences between opposed modes of history, “instead of preserving differences through

⁴² “Goodbye to Russia, Russia and Russia!: Finland’s New NATO Chapter Within the Framework of Shelter Theory,” *Uluslararası İlişkiler / International Relations* 21, no. 81 (2024): 34, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27317653>.

⁴³ Lavery, “Finlandization Interview.”

⁴⁴ Antero Holmilla and Pertti Ahonen, “The Good, the Bad and the Ugly: The Many Faces of Finlandization and Some Potential Lessons for Ukraine,” *Zeithistorische Forschungen / Studies in Contemporary History* 19, no. 3 (2022): 575, <https://doi.org/10.14765/zzf.dok-2473>.

⁴⁵ “What Is History in International Relations?” *Millennium: Journal of International Studies* 37, no. 2 (December 2008): 420, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0305829808097648>.

gatekeeping exercises or the policing of borders.”⁴⁶

Meibauer (2023) suggests a way to historicize neoclassical realist approaches by theorizing with history in two ways: at the unit level, where it affects the state domestically, or systematically, where it affects the international environment.⁴⁷ Mouritzen (2017) does something similar, suggesting that realism borrow from constructivism to combine interstate geopolitics and geoeconomics with intrastate history or “lessons of the past.” They explain that this shouldn’t be done for all states, but rather “*only* regarding the specific explanatory gap at stake.”⁴⁸

⁴⁶ 430.

⁴⁷ “Neorealism, Neoclassical Realism and the Problem(s) of History,” *International Relations* 37, no. 2 (June 2023): 361, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00471178211033943>.

⁴⁸ “Combining ‘Incompatible’ Foreign Policy Explanations: How a Realist Can Borrow from Constructivism,” *Journal of International Relations and Development* 20, no. 3 (July 1, 2017): 637, <https://doi.org/10.1057/jird.2016.2>.

Chapter 2: Finlandization as a Continuation of History

In Arter's (2023) article, he argues that a form of Finlandization continues based on four components as explained in *A "Post-Finlandization"*:

1. Continuation of Cold War mentality and Kekkonen-era preventative diplomacy in the 90s
2. Naïve belief in Russian democracy and human rights
3. A reluctance to respond to signs of Russian authoritarianism
4. An unquestionable policy of military non-alignment and credible defense

Arter lays out a convincing argument that indeed Finlandization continued in some form, at least outwardly. He brings up actions by Finnish leadership that display how Finnish diplomacy and foreign policy were hampered by an ongoing memory of the past. What the article fails to do however is discuss to the fullest extent what Finland did practically in terms of military coöperation, EU integration, and bilateral agreements following the Cold War. These two aspects seemingly work in contradiction; one presents Finland as an acquiescent nation, the other sees Finland building up its defense and integration. I intend to use Weislander's (2022) framework to analyze this aspect of Finnish policy, and make sense of how Arter's findings fit with these material policy changes.

Weislander's Framework

Weislander's (2022)⁴⁹ framework is based on Sweden's Hultqvist doctrine enacted in 2013. This non-aligned Hultqvist doctrine is defined by three things: "(1) a focus on building deterrence and national defence capabilities; (2) a patchwork of deepened bilateral arrangements, as well as an enhanced partnership with NATO, but no security guarantees; and (3) strong support for a rules-based security order and a tough stance against Russia, who has broken that order."⁵⁰ Here, she examines the claim by Minister Peter Hultqvist, author of the doctrine, who says that it simply a "continuation" of Sweden's previous non-alignment. Weislander examines the changes before

⁴⁹ Anna Wieslander, "'The Hultqvist Doctrine' – Swedish Security and Defence Policy After the Russian Annexation of Crimea," *Defence Studies* 22, no. 1 (January 2, 2022): 35–59, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14702436.2021.1955619>.

⁵⁰ 36.

and after 2013 of doctrine, levels of integrational policy, and levels of screening⁵¹. She assumes that an integrative policy would entail high levels of integration and low levels of screening, and non-alignment would be the opposite. Through this, Weislander finds that the doctrine is not a continuation of non-alignment, but rather a significant change in security policy. She concludes that the Hultqvist doctrine is not a “non-alignment policy” as politicians claim, but rather an integration policy, one that “seek[s] solutions through external engagement and partnerships.”⁵²

Wieslander concludes her article by suggesting other case studies of “small states pursuing integration strategies in face of external threats, without formally joining alliances” be done using her framework. She questions whether neoclassical realism is sufficient in explaining this kind of divergent behavior, with Finland being a clear counterpart to Sweden, and the country she suggests using the framework on next.⁵³ This is where I hope to start my research. To do so, like with Wieslander (2022), I need to explore the change or lack of change between the previous doctrine of Soviet-era Finlandization, and the newer doctrine of Post-Soviet “Post-Finlandization”. I will adopt Arter’s (2023) translation of the term here because it gives a name to the phenomenon and provides key features that make it easier to refer to and compare against.

Existing research on “Post-Finlandization”

Many articles describe how the effects of Cold War-era Finlandization persist, even if it is in passing. Most articles refer to it as a policy of “neutrality”, “non-alignment”, or “post-neutrality” (Arter 2023; Forsberg and Vaahtoranta 2001; Forsberg and Pesu 2016; Kulali Martin (2024); Migliorati 2024; Pakkasvirta and Tuominen 2024). In all of these, they do refer to Russia as an influencing factor.

Brommesson, Ekengren, and Michalski (2024) referred to this as “the old paradigm with a good working relationship with Russia”, always making sure to keep Russia in mind when making policy

⁵¹ In her words, “screening refers to measures taken by a state to ensure national freedom of action, and to reduce dependency on a great power and its institutional structures.”

⁵² “‘The Hultqvist Doctrine’ – Swedish Security and Defence Policy After the Russian Annexation of Crimea,” 52.

⁵³ 53.

decisions.⁵⁴ In an older article, Forsberg and Vaahtoranta (2001) describe this ongoing phenomenon as a “post-neutrality”. They argue that while geopolitical and historical factors still affect the decision making process of Finnish leaders a decade later, Russia’s influence was beginning to wane.⁵⁵ This article is especially useful in providing a closer analysis of the before and after of the policy change.

In contrast, Migliorati (2024) describes that in the transition from Soviet to Post-Soviet eras, Finland shifted from neutrality to a “vague reframing as ‘non-alignment’”. They continue further to explain that this non-aligned stance is held in contradiction to pragmatic actions taken by the country e.g. pursuing NATO and EU involvement.⁵⁶ Pesu (2017) takes this a step further and claims that non-alignment’s relevance has declined over the past three decades. He explains that Finland has “systematically de-institutionalized – or divested itself of – non-alignment,” through years of international defense coöperation.⁵⁷ Unlike the majority of other sources, Migliorati (2024) is one of the few to take the stance that neutrality ended after the Cold War, along with Wiberg (2023).

Aunesluoma and Rainio-Niemi (2016) argue against this position, stating that had Finnish neutrality simply been a pragmatic choice taken to survive then a clear change in policy would have taken place after the fall of the USSR. Instead, they observe that Finnish posturing, decision making, and diplomacy were still influenced by an enduring identity, not pragmatism, of neutrality formed during the Cold War regardless of pragmatic actions.⁵⁸ In their opinion, Finnish restructuring of neutrality to non-alignment when joining the EU was heavily influenced by this core identity, and thus neutrality continued to persist after 1989, even if challenged by integration.⁵⁹ This is in

⁵⁴ “From Variation to Convergence in Turbulent Times – Foreign and Security Policy Choices Among the Nordics 2014–2023,” *European Security* 33, no. 1 (January 2, 2024): 28, 35, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662839.2023.2221185>.

⁵⁵ “Inside the EU, Outside NATO: Paradoxes of Finland’s and Sweden’s Post-neutrality,” *European Security* 10, no. 1 (March 1, 2001): 88, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09662830108407483>.

⁵⁶ “New Nordic Pathways? Explaining Nordic Countries’ Defence Policy Choices in the Wake of the Ukrainian War,” *Journal of European Public Policy* 31, no. 10 (October 2, 2024): 3263, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2024.2314247>.

⁵⁷ Matti Pesu, “What Non-Alignment? Finland’s Security and Defence Policy Stems from Partnerships” (Finnish Institute of International Affairs, November 16, 2017), 3, <https://www.fia.fi/en/publication/finlands-security-and-defence-policy-stems-from-partnerships>.

⁵⁸ “Neutrality as Identity?: Finland’s Quest for Security in the Cold War,” *Journal of Cold War Studies* 18, no. 4 (2016): 62, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26925640>.

⁵⁹ 77.

agreement with Tiilikainen (2006), who states that Finnish identity didn't change after the Cold War. She concedes that it seems like Finland's EU policy in the 1990s to be a change from neutrality to European integration, and goes on to explain how Finland integrated rapidly and enthusiastically with the EU. They, however, say that the same "small state" identity remained and influenced every decision they made within the EU.⁶⁰ Pakkasvirta and Tuominen (2024) add on to explain that in 1995, upon joining the EU, Finland officially ended its neutrality, replacing it instead with a policy of military non-alignment. However, even with this nominal change in policy, they argue that actions taken and documents produced by the government prove that Cold War-era neutrality persists in some form.⁶¹ Kulali Martin (2024) takes a slightly different position, saying that even with a ramp up in integration, only the application to NATO in 2022 officially ended the Cold War-informed non-alignment.⁶²

Forsberg and Vaahtoranta (2001) support this idea of a rapid change by explaining the tradition of neutrality isn't nearly as strong in Finland as it is in its neighbor Sweden. This is important as with the fall of the Soviet Union and its accession to the EU, Finland is on a more equal level with Sweden and is less dependent on its traditionally neutral decision making. Finland became free to make decisions of its own e.g. joining the Economic and Monetary Union. "In short, Finland is no longer the poor cousin that needs Sweden to pave the way, or the threatened neighbor that desperately needs the protection of Sweden."⁶³

Arter (2023) is the only article among my sources that gives a clear outline of what this phenomenon is. He defines this ongoing post-Soviet Finlandization as "Post-Finlandization," a translation of the Finnish *jälkisuomettuminen*, a term coined by National Coalition chair Petteri Orpo in 2022.⁶⁴

Forsberg and Pesu (2016) reject this term and instead propose the use of "counter-Finlandised" to mean "Russia now appear[ing] in a negative light and the media refrain[ing] from reporting

⁶⁰ "Finland — An EU Member with a Small State Identity," *Journal of European Integration* 28, no. 1 (March 1, 2006): 85, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036330500480599>.

⁶¹ "From Cold War 'Neutrality' to the West," 37.

⁶² "Goodbye to Russia, Russia and Russia!" 34.

⁶³ "Inside the EU, Outside NATO," 71.

⁶⁴ "From Finlandisation and Post-Finlandisation to the End of Finlandisation?" 176.

positive news on Russia.”⁶⁵ This frames Finlandization as a negative response to Russia, rather than a positive response like that of the Soviet-era. They also bring up the idea of “re-Finlandisation”, an idea brought up by critics of Finland’s cautiousness with Russia, and its perceived failure to respond to Russian issues of democracy and human rights.⁶⁶

Modifying the framework

While certainly compelling in the case of Sweden, and perhaps elucidating in evaluating Arter’s (2023) claim that post-Finlandization is a continuation of Cold War-era Finlandization, there are a few issues in just directly porting over the framework.

The first issue is finding a proper time to place the change in doctrine. Unlike the Hultqvist doctrine, post-Finlandization doesn’t exactly have an explicit changeover date. Some argue that that era of Finlandization ended with the end of the Cold War, other state it ended with the end of Kekkonen’s presidency, and others argue for another date.⁶⁷

The second issue with the framework is fact that change in post-Finlandization was a gradual process with multiple phases. Certainly, EU accession was a big step by Finland after the dissolution of the Soviet Union, but simply examining that point compared to just a few years before won’t, in my opinion, reveal much about Finland 5 or 10 years after that point. The largest changes in Finland policy came later down the line, as it slowly began to open up and its fear of Russia regrew.

To address the first issue, I have selected 1992 as my start date for post-Finlandization. My reasoning behind this is because this is when the USSR collapsed, marking an important shift in Finland’s foreign policy. Finland’s previous decision-making always keep the Soviet Union in mind; with its downfall, Finland would have to adapt accordingly, at least in theory.

The second issue is a little more complicated. Instead of comparing one period to another and being done, I will split the “post-Finlandized” period into multiple smaller sections and compare those each to the original Finlandized period. The periods that I will split post-Cold War-era

⁶⁵ “The ‘Finlandisation’ of Finland,” 486.

⁶⁶ 486.

⁶⁷ Nevakivi, *Miten Kekkonen pääsi valtaan ja Suomi suomettui*; Lavery, “Finlandization Interview.”

Finlandization into are:

1. 1992-2007 (Fall of USSR/Beginning of EU Accession to Signing of the Treaty of Lisbon)
2. 2007-2014 (Signing of the Treaty of Lisbon to Invasion of Crimea)
3. 2014-2022 (Invasion of Crimea to Invasion of Ukraine)

The reason why I selected the start date to be 1992 is that the USSR dissolved in December of 1991 and Finland applied for EU accession right after in January of 1992, marking the first large change in Finland's connection to the West. 2009 was selected as that is when Finland signed the Treaty of Lisbon, another major commitment and opened up Finland to the possibility of further military integration. 2014 is the year that Russia annexed Crimea, changing the calculus in Finnish security, and 2022 is the year of the greatest change: Finnish accession into NATO.

I will still maintain Wieslander's framework of separating the doctrinal components, integrational components, and screening components. What will be changing, however, is the content of the doctrinal components. In the Hulqvist doctrine, the three components as defined by Weislander (2017) are: 1) a strong defense, 2) international defense cooperation, and 3) a rule-based order. [@] Finland's doctrinal components will be different. I will use the components that are explicitly outlined in the 2001 Finnish Security and Defence Policy: 1) a credible defense capability, 2) militarily non-allied, and 3) international cooperation.⁶⁸ I am using the 2001 report for the components because it lines up neatly with views expressed in writing and in speeches in the 1990s, and is the first to be written down explicitly in an official strategy document following the fall of the USSR.⁶⁹

The official policy

As explained above, the official policy established in the early 90s is maintained in a very similar format into the early 2000s, only explicitly changing slightly over the years as geopolitical realities change.

⁶⁸ Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2001," VNS 2/2001 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, June 13, 2001), <https://www.defmin.fi/files/1147/selonteko2001.pdf>.

⁶⁹ Martti Ahtisaari, "Address by President Martti Ahtisaari at the Annual Meeting of the National Defence Courses," <https://www.eilen.fi/en/1989/?language=en>; Przemysław Osiewicz, "The Comparison of the Finnish Security Policy in 1990 and 2002," *Środkowoeuropejskie Studia Polityczne*, no. 1 (June 15, 2005): 139, <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssp.2005.1.11>.

“Military non-alignment” (*sotilaallinen liittoutumattomuus*) is mentioned frequently during this period, in documents and in speeches. Distinct from neutrality, what it entails is essentially just a limit against anything that would commit Finland to mutual defense agreements. A reason expressed in many of the parliamentary documents for this policy stance is that joining mutual defense agreements may be threatening to “neighbors” and the country doesn’t want to exacerbate any tenuous stability in the region.

A “credible defense capability” (*uskottava puolustuskyky*) is the linchpin to Finland’s position of military non-alignment. By fielding a believable defense, Finland proactively prevents the creation of future threats. Future threats would challenge Finland’s lack of security guarantees, a large reason why it eventually joined NATO in 2022. Credible defense in this case not only meant maintaining a large number of reservists, but also preparing all society for war in what is called “total defense”.

Coöperation (*yhteistyö*) is a common theme across military, political, and economic sectors as a way to promote stability. For the military, coöperation is a means towards crisis preparedness, future conflict readiness, and alignment signaling. Political and economic coöperation helps Finland promote its agenda through increasing its influence in the EU, spreading democracy regionally, and strengthening its domestic economic. All of which in turn promote regional and domestic security.

Applying the framework

In this section, like with Wieslander (2022), I examine the main components of the post-Cold War doctrine in light of the assumption that, given Finland’s history, an extension of Finlandized policy would include central elements of continuity, rather than change. On the other hand, a substantial amount of new elements would indicate a clear shift of policy.

1992-2007

Context

Immediately following the fall of the Soviet Union, the geopolitical landscape was completely upended. Finland, who had long been practicing a balancing act between East and West, found that

it needed to restructure its foreign policy. The biggest change that this caused was a shift from the longstanding practice of neutrality, to a new military non-alignment. This change opened up to the possibility of joining the EU, providing a means of economic and military security, but also political influence to exert on Russia in a bid to stabilize the new state. Finland realized it was in its best interest to try and support the newly democratic Russian state, but was always aware of the possibility of backsliding. The Finnish government believed that stability could be promoted through non-alignment and international cooperation.⁷⁰ However, the question of replacing neutrality with non-alignment was a universally agreed upon decision. To some the idea of EU-membership was not compatible with neutrality, to others it was breaking with decades of precedent.⁷¹ However the instability of the crumbling USSR and with famously neutral nations Sweden and Austria joining the EU, Finland's perception towards neutrality and membership began to change.⁷²

Credible defense

The first element of Finland's post-Cold War doctrine is a large focus on a credible defense. This means building and sustaining a functioning military force, large and legitimate enough to deter adversaries.

During the Cold War, the idea of credible defense was core part of Finland's overarching defense planning. Finland had a reasonably sized active duty military at around 35,000, but its real strength came from the conscription process, which by the 90s, conscripted around 30,000 men each year. Conscription provided the country with a humungous reservist force: around 700,000 at its peak.⁷³ Formerly conscripted men were kept up-to-date with frequent refresher training, ensuring a high level of mobilization readiness. This, however, was on the decline since the 70s due in part to the

⁷⁰ Valtioneuvosto, "Turvallisuus muuttuvassa maailmassa: Suomen turvallisuuspolitiikan suuntalinjat," VNS 1/1995 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, June 6, 1995), 44, https://www.defmin.fi/files/246/2513_2143_selonteko95_1_.pdf.

⁷¹ Paavo Väyrynen, "Kirjallinen kysymys: Euroopan unionin jäsenyyden vaikutuksista Suomen ulko- ja puolustuspolitiikkaan," KK 562/1992 (Helsingissä: Eduskunta, December 4, 1992), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/Kysymys/Documents/kk_562+1992.pdf.

⁷² Valtioneuvosto, "Suomi Ja Euroopan Yhteisön Jäsenyys," VNS 2/1991 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, January 9, 1992), 37, https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_2+1991.pdf.

⁷³ Eric Solsten, Sandra W. Meditz, and Library Of Congress, *Finland : A Country Study* (Washington, D.C.: Federal Research Division, 1990), 315, <https://www.loc.gov/item/89600315/>.

aging population, and with it the reserve numbers declined.⁷⁴ Conscription however was not the only feature of a credible defense. A core tenet of the Finnish defense doctrine was the concept of a total defense: the idea that all of society has a role to play in planning a defense. Logistical infrastructure was made with defense in mind, with bridges, roads, and others important means of transportation being made for both daily use and in case of war. Shelters, stockpiles, and wartime contingencies were made, and urban planning occasionally included evacuation and shelter plans. However, the willingness of the public to defend Finland against attack was only around 50% in 1970. This leapt to 68% in 1982, possibly related to the death of Brezhnev.⁷⁵

After the Cold War, much of the same sentiment remained. Finland was to maintain its credible defense, something that was credited for keeping territorial integrity together. The concept of total defense was kept as well, continuing to prepare society in case of war; the willingness to defend Finland against attack reached an all new high of 78% in 1992.⁷⁶ What changed however was the budget put towards the military and the focus of the Finland's defense activities shifted from a focus on full on territorial defense to one that was more scaled down, focused on crisis management and international coöperation. Although the defense budget shrunk immediately after the fall of the USSR, it eventually rebounded, reaching comparable levels in 1998 and 2004.⁷⁷

The large military that it was fielded was substituted in part with things like NATO's Partnership for Peace (PfP) and in smaller part by the EU's CFSP. While these organizations didn't provide Finland any security guarantees, it did provide Finland an opportunity to expand its interoperability with Western military forces, increase sources of intelligence, and publicly signal where its allegiances lie. This increased the effectiveness of any future military collaboration, allowed better adaption to the growing threat field, and grew Finland's influence in Europe's security; all working to provide

⁷⁴ Olli-Pekka Jalonen and Unto Vesa, "Something Old, Something New, Something Borrowed, Something Blue: Finland's Defence Policy in a Changing Security Environment," *Cooperation and Conflict* 27, no. 4 (December 1, 1992): 382, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010836792027004003>.

⁷⁵ MTS, "Suomalaisten mielipiteitä ulko- ja turvallisuuspolitiikasta, maanpuolustuksesta ja turvallisuudesta," Maanpuolustustiedotuksen suunnittelukunta, tiedotteita ja katsauksia 2024:4 (Helsingissä: Puolustusministeriö, December 4, 2024), 18, <https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/handle/10024/165931>.

⁷⁶ MTS, 18.

⁷⁷ Tuomas A. Pernu, "The Finnish Defense Forces' Budget, 1986-2020: Analysis of Funding Variability" (Naval Postgraduate School, 2021), <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/trecms/AD1164977>.

the nation with a sense of security(?). By 2004, the number of conscripts fell, fluctuating around the 27,000 mark. Reservists numbers stayed about the same, thanks to the growing population. Between these two periods, the population's willingness to defend the territory sharply increased from 42% in the 1971 poll to 67% in the 1982 poll.⁷⁸

Military non-alignment

The second part of the post-Cold War doctrine is the commitment to military non-alignment, which in practice just meant nothing that made any security guarantees like NATO's Article 5. This was similarly practiced as well during the Cold War, but to a greater extent. Instead of just the restriction of no mutual defense agreements, Finland was fully neutral. It took on no alliances and in general limited all actions that could be perceived as leaning West or East. This neutrality, however, was in service of appeasing the USSR, i.e. Finlandization. The neutrality of Finland was necessitated by the YYA-treaty, which prevented it from doing anything that the Soviet Union did not want it to do. Economically the two were tied together, both commercially and militarily, and any disruption to their relationship could spell disaster financially: exactly what happened after the end of the Cold War. Although Finland made sure to keep a consistent presentation of neutrality or at times, Soviet interests, it did join organizations that aligned it elsewhere. The Nordic Council and the EFTA all were ways that Finland outwardly interfaced with the West, but always in a cautious manner, presenting its neutrality forward. Informally, Finland conducted "understandings" with Sweden, discussing how the two would coordinate defenses if the USSR attacked. Finland also purchased equipment and vehicles from Western nations in limited quantity, but still deepening its connections.⁷⁹ These interactions were always limited and Finland during this period always made sure to make the USSR feel safe and secure in any action it made.

Finnish participation in military related international, regional, and bilateral agreements expanded greatly after the Cold War. Joining the European Community was a huge change in how Finland

⁷⁸ MTS, "Suomalaisten mielipiteitä ulko- ja turvallisuuspolitiikasta, maanpuolustuksesta ja turvallisuudesta."

⁷⁹ Charly Salenius-Pasternak and Henri Vanhanen, "Finnish-Swedish defence cooperation: What history suggests about future scenarios - FIIA - Finnish Institute of International Affairs" (Finnish Institute of International Affairs, June 3, 2020), 4, <https://fii.fi/julkaisu/finnish-swedish-defence-cooperation>.

participated with the international community. The EC made it party to the CFSP, further integrating its military with the West. Before that, Finland joined NATO's PfP and began actively conducting military exercises with NATO members, promoting interoperability and readiness with NATO troops. This was a huge divergence from the Cold War, where it would exercise solely on its own. A few years later it would join NATO's Euro-Atlantic Partnership Council, furthering its lean to the West. A visible doctrinal change was that official defense white papers in this era began to explicitly name Russia as a potential challenge, something that would have been unthinkable during the era of Cold War Finlandization. Bilaterally, Finland began working closer with Sweden and the U.S. on military and intelligence matters, spreading its roots further and further outwards. However, Finland maintained its status of military non-alignment in its white papers, with 7 explicit mentions in the 2001 Security and Defence Policy report and 4 explicit mentions in the 2004 report.

International coöperation

The last element of Finland's post-Cold War doctrine was the focus on international coöperation. Coöperation militarily, economically, and politically serve as means for Finland to strengthen regional security and stability. Coöperation during the Cold War was limited, especially as leaders feared any action would be perceived as a threat by the USSR. However, Finland did find ways to work internationally. The country participated frequently in UN Peacekeeping such as with UNIFIL in Lebanon and UNFICYP in Cyprus, offering up its forces to spread peace and cultivate its symbol as a leader in conflict resolution.⁸⁰ Most visibly however, Helsinki served as a host and mediator for international accords between East and West. Agreements like the Helsinki Accords and SALT Accords were all done in Helsinki, bridging East and West. In these, Finland was not overtly acting to spread peace, but instead using soft power to facilitate peace between each of the two sides that it was sandwiched between.

This coöperation expanded greatly after the Cold War. Now rid of any formal neutral restriction placed by the YYA-treaty, Finland was free to seek out activities that would have once been seen as

⁸⁰ Puolustusvoimat, "Kansainvälinen toiminta" (Puolustusvoimat, 2025), <https://puolustusvoimat.fi/kansainvalinen-toiminta>.

threatening to the USSR. This included joining the EU, adopting the Euro, and joining the Schengen Area. This tied Finland's economy to the West, something direly needed after its largest trading partner in the USSR collapsed. NATO's PfP and Euro-Atlantic Partnership Council were another organization that characterized Finland's international participation during this period, with defense whitepapers emphasizing readiness, resilience, and interoperability, and presented EU and NATO partnerships as central to Finnish security.⁸¹ Finland also expanded in its amount of peacekeeping missions, from only UN missions to include NATO and EU missions like ISAF in Afghanistan, KFOR in Kosovo, and EUFOR Althea in Bosnia and Herzegovina.⁸²

Levels of Integration

To assess the level of integration, I follow Weislander's (2022) assumption that integration is stronger when it is (1) marked by openness and transparency, (2) involves a broad range of states and institutions, and (3) embraces not only peacetime cooperation but conflict and war.

Openness and transparency about Finland's efforts to integrate with states and international institutions to maximize security was extremely limited during the Cold War. Finnish officials would regularly espouse a position while doing something else behind the scenes. Any action made to integrate with the West was either approached with great caution or done entirely covertly. This dimension has improved after 1992, where Finland more clearly signals what side it on. Its white papers more clearly express its intent, and it works with organizations and nations more openly than during the Cold War. However, as Arter (2023) argued, there are still elements during this period where the true intent of the government was suppressed in order appease Russia.

Finland during 1992 to 2007 worked with a vast array of states and institutions. The work it did during this time period with Nordic, European and Transatlantic bodies only existed in much more limited forms before 1992. Finland stuck as true to its neutrality as possible, obligated by the YYA-treaty and Soviet intervention.

⁸¹ Valtioneuvosto, "Suomen Osallistumisesta EU:n Sotilaalliseen Kriisinhallintaoperaatioon Bosnia-Hertsegovinassa (Althea)," VNS 5/2004 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, September 6, 2004), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_5+2004.pdf.

⁸² Puolustusvoimat, "Kansainvälinen toiminta."

The third dimension, as Wieslander (2022) explains, concerns whether coöperation occurs during both peacetime *and* conflict and war. In this regard, Finland changed the most. All coöperation during the Cold War was either in the form of politics or economics. Military planning and integration was solely domestic; again due to fear from the USSR. After the Cold War, Finland grew its international coöperation to encompass both crisis management and defense scenarios, working to improve interoperability of its military with NATO and EU member nations.⁸³

Levels of screening

As explained earlier, screening refers to measures taken by a state to ensure freedom of action, and to reduce dependency on a great power and its institutional structures.

Screening was a core part of Finland's identity for years. Even more so than Sweden, Finland as a small state needed to find a way to navigate itself between great power conflicts to survive. While it was indeed bound by the YYA-treaty, this treaty didn't as much tie the two nations together as it separated Finland from all others. Aspirationally, Finland did all it could otherwise to be self-sufficient even while limited. During the Cold War, it existed outside of alliances, working to balance itself to maintain an independent position between East and West.

After 1992, screening began to decrease. Finland began participating in EU crisis management programs and NATO's PfP, but always voluntarily and always made sure it had say over arrangements. This was a common theme for the period: growing participation with outside institutions and powers, but still maintaining primary decision-making over issues of relevance.⁸⁴

Domestic circumstances

From a realistic point of view, the great power dynamics surrounding Finland should cause it to seek shelter in the form of alliances and security guarantees. But instead, even after the fall of the Soviet Union, it maintained a policy of military non-alignment. This is best explained by domestic circumstances.

⁸³ Valtioneuvosto, "Turvallisuus muuttuvassa maailmassa."

⁸⁴ Valtioneuvosto, "Pitkän Aikavälin Tulevaisuudesta," VNS 3/1993 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, October 13, 1992), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_3+1993.pdf.

Some scholars may point towards Finlandization, but I argue that during this early post-Cold War period, Finland's reluctance to join outside commitments stemmed primarily from a historic fear of loss of control, a commitment to not escalating tensions, and most impactfully a lack of public support. Finland's strong policy stance to maintain stability is expressed throughout all of their white papers during this period.⁸⁵ With an unstable Russia to their East, joining a mutual defense agreement was seen as only further destabilizing the region.⁸⁶ By playing a balancing act between East and West, Helsinki believed that democracy, rule of law, and human rights could be promoted in Russia, with trickledown effects into the region as a whole.⁸⁷

The lack of public support is related to this idea of not wanting to upset a balance. The majority of the public saw no need for mutual defense. There was a consistent domestic weariness against foreign commitments, with even EU accession drawing some concerns of loss of control when it came to military commitments.⁸⁸

The primary factor tying all of these together was the enduring memory of Finland's experience with Russia and historic role a neutral state between East and West.⁸⁹ No one, from the public to the government, wanted to lose sovereignty again. Not only was the memory of Finlandization fresh in the mind, but lessons from WWII and 1800s Russification of Finland painted a vivid picture of how easily Finland could lose itself due to its neighbor once again. Very visible actions were weighed against this possibility, and a mutual defense agreement did not win out.⁹⁰

⁸⁵ Valtioneuvosto, "Suomen EU-politiikan Suuntaviivat," VNS 3/1994 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, February 14, 1995), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_3+1994.pdf.

⁸⁶ Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2004," VNS 6/2004 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, September 24, 2004), https://www.defmin.fi/files/311/2574_2160_English_White_paper_2004_1_.pdf.

⁸⁷ Valtioneuvosto, "Euroopan turvallisuuskehitys ja Suomen puolustus," VNS 1/1997 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, March 17, 1997), https://www.defmin.fi/ministerion_teemat/puolustuselonteot/suomen_turvallisuus_ja_puolustuspoliittinen_selonteko_1997; Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2001."

⁸⁸ Väyrynen, "Euroopan unionin jäsenyyden vaikutuksista Suomen ulko- ja puolustuspolitiikkaan."

⁸⁹ Valtioneuvosto, "Ajankohtaisista Ulkopoliittisista Kysymyksistä," VNS 1/1991 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, November 14, 1991), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_1+1991.pdf.

⁹⁰ Valtioneuvosto, "Euroopan unionin tulevaisuudesta," VNS 3/2001 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, December 14, 2001), https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/vaski/selonteko/Documents/vns_3+2001.pdf.

2007-2014

2007 was yet another turning point, albeit not one as drastic as 1992. While the EU grew as an institution and the Baltic region slowly stabilized, Russia began showing more signs of aggressiveness. This development did not go unnoticed by Finland who expressed concern about Russia's actions, especially in the Baltic Sea and the ongoing Chechen War.⁹¹ The recent cyberattacks on Estonia via Russian nationals, widely believed to be organized by the Kremlin, sparked internal concern in the Finnish government. It was under this steadily growing tension that the Treaty of Lisbon was signed, restructuring and strengthening the EU, but more importantly in this case also introducing the possibility of a Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO). While its reception was lukewarm at the time, it paved a way in the future for the EU to enable the common defense clause created in Article 42 of the Maastricht Treaty.⁹²

Credible defense

This period was not too different from the one before it, with continued conscription and reservist program and cooperation with NATO and the EU to develop troop capability and interoperability. Where it did change was that the Finnish security policy started to shift away from focusing solely territorial defense to also include expeditionary and CSDP-relevant capabilities. While the main task of the Defense Forces continued to be “independently repelling [an] attack,” the 2009 Security and Defense Policy report highlighted throughout a need to add on international military crisis management.⁹³ The limited cooperation from 1992-2007 grew to full participation in EU Battlegroups, the CSDP, and NATO peacekeeping missions. This allowed the Defense Forces to develop practical experience in not only crisis management, but also operating with friendly forces that may or may not come to their help in case of war. Domestically, the population's willingness to defend the territory declined over period from 76% in 2007 to 70% in 2013.⁹⁴

⁹¹ Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2004,” 67.

⁹² Pesu, “What Non-Alignment?” 5.

⁹³ Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2009,” VNS 1/2009 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, June 23, 2009), 68.

⁹⁴ MTS, “Suomalaisten mielipiteitä ulko- ja turvallisuuspolitiikasta, maanpuolustuksesta ja turvallisuudesta.”

Military non-alignment

While there was still no mutual defense agreements during this period, Finland took action to more closely ally with Western powers. Interestingly, non-alignment is only mentioned once in each the 2009 and the 2012 Security and Defence Policy reports.⁹⁵

Within the EU, Finland adopted the Treaty of Lisbon which included a clause in Article 42 about mutual solidarity. While not a mandatory clause, it was a large step for Finland in terms of its posture: displaying that it would be willing to tolerate the idea of mutual assistance. The entire concept of mutual assistance goes against the core tenet of non-alignment. (??) The clause is rationalized in the Security and Defence Policy papers by explaining that it up to the Member State to choose what kind of form of assistance is provided, i.e. Finland will not be obligated to go to war if the clause is invoked.⁹⁶

Within NATO, the Defense Forces were more actively developed to be interoperable through the PfP Planning and Review Process and the Operational Capabilities Concept. Primarily in order to enhance crisis management, Finland participated in activities supplementing the NATO Response Force. Again, as a bonus, this gave the Defense Forces practical experience that would be applicable elsewhere. This was a common theme for this time period; a focus on international crisis management as a means for strengthening domestic defense. As explained by Jyri Häkämies, Defence Minister at the time, “The more stable the European continent remains, the safer will Finland be. As a consequence, our forces continue to be involved in NATO-and EU-led operations, be it in the Balkans, Africa, or even in a far-away Afghanistan.”⁹⁷

Most impactfully, Finland formed NORDEFECO with the other Nordics in 2009, creating a network of close coöperation not only on military military training and organization, but also intelligence sharing and armament interoperability. Finland engaged in defense training overseas,

⁹⁵ Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2009,” 69; Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2012,” VNS 6/2012 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvosto, March 15, 2013), 99.

⁹⁶ Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2009,” 72; Valtioneuvosto, “Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2012,” 89.

⁹⁷ Jyri Häkämies, “Minister of Defence Jyri Häkämies at CSIS in Washington” (Speech, Washington, D.C., June 9, 2007), https://www.defmin.fi/en/topical/speeches/minister_of_defence_jyri_hakamies_at_csis_in_washington.3335.news?663_o=10.

not yet allowing exercises on home soil. Within this framework, Finland increasingly participated in joint exercises, especially with Sweden.⁹⁸ However, no formal bilateral agreements were yet signed.

International coöperation

Finland continued to build from the previous period, increasing the amount and depth of international engagements. As mentioned beforehand, Finland formed NORDEFECO with the other Nordic nations, deepening its coöperation with its neighbors. Finland also joined the Northern Group, an informal forum led by the UK to discuss issues of security and stability. Established in 2012, it involves the five Nordic countries, the three Baltic countries, Poland, the Netherlands, and Germany.

Finland continued participating in UN and NATO peacekeeping missions in an expanded capacity. It maintained its commitment of forces to ISAF in Afghanistan, KFOR in Kosovo, but added others like MINURCAT in Chad and UNMISS in South Sudan. Peacekeeping continued to be a way for Finland to demonstrate its values, build trust internationally, and develop experience.⁹⁹ In addition to the traditional peacekeeping missions that have long made up Finland's international coöperation, Finland routinely took part in Crisis Management Exercises (CMX) with NATO. Focused on broader security threats like terrorism, cybersecurity, and nuclear proliferation, the exercises were not explicitly about collective defense, but increased coöperation between Finland and NATO forces.¹⁰⁰ This added activity shows a deepening of Finnish participation in the international community, especially in the West.

Levels of Integration

The level of openness continued during this period with actions generally being clear, but at times having a level of obfuscation due to ongoing appeasement as explained by Arter (2023). Was such example of the lack of clarity comes from the reception of Defence Minister Häkämies's speech

⁹⁸ Saloniemi-Pasternak and Vanhanen, "Finnish-Swedish defence cooperation," 4.

⁹⁹ Puolustusvoimat, "Kansainvälinen toiminta."

¹⁰⁰ NATO, "NATO Crisis Management Exercise 2009 (CMX 09) from 4 to 10 March 2010," Press Release (2010) 025 (NATO, March 4, 2010), http://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_61743.htm.

in D.C. in 2007. In the speech he explain's Finland's policy of non-alignment and international coöperation. Fairly standard in terms of following the policy line, he diverges from it when he states that the world's three main security challenges are "Russia, Russia, and Russia."¹⁰¹ The speech was immediately criticized by Prime Minister Halonen among other politicians and was seen as harming Finnish interests; Häkämies claimed to only be stating the Finnish defense policy clearly and openly.¹⁰² The same is reflected in the 2009 and 2012 white papers, saying that Russia's policies are "of interest" to Finland and treating Russian policies with nuance and care. Much is said about working with Russia to improve stability, always framing issues to limit accusations or blame.¹⁰³

The spread of actors that Finland worked with grew, especially in terms of NATO missions and exercises and with regional organizations. Finland continued to work with them in both on military and non-military contexts, but with a growth in military activities. The willingness to accept the Treaty of Lisbon and its common defense clause certainly shifted the balance as well.

Levels of screening

While Finland increased dependency on Western nations through increasing political, economic, and military ties, it still continued to affirm the right to not get called into any mandatory military deployments. This can be seen best through their rationale around the Treaty of Lisbon's mutual assistance clause, frequently reiterating that the clause allows the state to choose how any assistance is provided. In regards to NATO, Finland states in the 2009 Security and Defence Policy report that they have been able to "participate in a crisis management manner it considers appropriate." This sentiment is so strong that the government expresses that even if Finland joins NATO, they would "independently decide on participation in operations" and not fall for any political pressure.¹⁰⁴ Finland continues to keep NATO membership as an option, but expresses that it primarily wants to build security through stronger strategic partnerships and a promotion of the "European neighborhood".

¹⁰¹ Häkämies, "Minister of Defence Jyri Häkämies at CSIS in Washington."

¹⁰² Jessikka Aro, "Näkökulma: "Venäjä, Venäjä, Venäjä" – Suomen keskeinen turvallisuushaaste vai mörköleikin kehittäjä" (Yle Uutiset, November 19, 2014), <https://yle.fi/a/3-7460097>.

¹⁰³ Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2009"; Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2012."

¹⁰⁴ Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2009," 80.

Domestic circumstances

Domestic circumstances remained relatively the same. While there were some new voices in the government supporting a reassessment of security policies, much of the same reluctance continued both in the political elite and the greater populace. One such voice of support was Foreign Minister Alexander Stubb, who viewed the Russo-Georgian War as a turning point for Finland, but didn't want to make any hasty decisions about NATO membership yet. Accession latency and close cooperation continued to be sufficient for many leaders in providing the security required.¹⁰⁵

2014-2022

2014 was the year Russia invaded and annexed Ukraine, shocking the European security environment. The annexation washed away the enduring perception that military conflict between European states was a thing of the past.¹⁰⁶ Russia was centered again in the minds of Finns, but not enough to change outward policy. The public was still overwhelmingly against NATO, but the invasion reignited discussion on national defense, regional security, and military readiness. Concerns were raised in government about possible changes in policy, but official responses assured that no extensive reforms need be made.¹⁰⁷

Credible defense

Following Russia's invasion of Crimea, Finland began a new but familiar period of defense. Much like in an era past, there was a refocus on territorial defense and an increase in the defense budget. Just a few months after the invasion, Finland signed a memorandum of understanding with NATO allowing member nations to hold joint exercises on Finnish territory and accepting aid from NATO members in crisis/threat scenarios. Along with this memorandum came additional exercises

¹⁰⁵ Tuomas Forsberg, "Four Rounds of the Finnish NATO Debate," *Nordic Review of International Studies*, no. 1, 1 (June 1, 2023): 41–50, <https://nr.is.journal.fi/article/view/125327>.

¹⁰⁶ Erkki Tuomioja, "Kirjallinen kysymys: Venäjän asemaan ja uhkakuviin reagoiminen Suomessa," KK 159/2014 (Helsingissä: Eduskunta, March 18, 2014), 3, <https://www.eduskunta.fi/FI/Vaski/sivut/trip.aspx?triptype=ValtiopivaAsiat&docid=kk+159/2014>.

¹⁰⁷ Tuomioja, 4.

and readiness preparation through becoming an Enhanced Opportunities Partner.¹⁰⁸ International coöperation in the form of crisis readiness was no longer a supporting goal, but one core to national defense, providing a direct pathway to improving the Defence Forces' capabilities.¹⁰⁹ While conscription numbers have continued to fall toward the 21,000 mark, it was made up by ongoing modernization efforts.¹¹⁰ Defense spending increased

Finland at the time, along with Sweden, were considered “more integrated in NATO on the operational and tactical level than many NATO members.”¹¹¹ Within the populace, there was an uptick in the willingness to defend the territory, leaping from around 70% to 77%.¹¹²

Military non-alignment

Russia's aggression into Crimea, while not yet pushing Finland to seek shelter with NATO, did cause Finland to start to expand its integration with military alliances and organizations. NORDEFECO, created in 2009, was incrementally upgraded and by 2021 its members had all signed agreements of increased coöperation, making it easier to act together in peace, crisis, or conflict.¹¹³

NATO accession as an option became clearer, with the most recent Foreign and Security Policy report following the invasion explicitly saying that Finland “maintains the option to seek NATO membership” with no further condition.¹¹⁴ This kind of statement does not appear in this form without qualification in any other security whitepapers of previous time periods; the 2012 report expressly says that “Finland is not preparing to apply for NATO membership during the present

¹⁰⁸ Migliorati, “New Nordic Pathways?” 3257.

¹⁰⁹ Valtioneuvosto, “Government Report on Finnish Foreign and Security Policy,” VNS 6/2016 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvoston kanslia, December 23, 2016), 27, <https://valtioneuvosto.fi/documents/10616/1986338/VNKJ092016+en.pdf>; Valtioneuvosto, “Government's Defence Report,” VNS 7/2017 (Helsingissä: Valtioneuvoston kanslia, February 16, 2017), 17, https://www.defmin.fi/files/3688/J07_2017_Governments_Defence_Report_Eng_PLM_160217.pdf.

¹¹⁰ Emma Jonsson et al., “Multifaceted Conscription: A Comparative Study of Six European Countries,” *Scandinavian Journal of Military Studies* 7, no. 1 (March 5, 2024): 22, <https://doi.org/10.31374/sjms.166>.

¹¹¹ Andrew Cottey, *The European Neutrals and NATO: Non-alignment, Partnership, Membership?*, 1st ed., New Security Challenges (London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2017), 86, <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-59524-9>.

¹¹² MTS, “Suomalaisten mielipiteitä ulko- ja turvallisuuspolitiikasta, maanpuolustuksesta ja turvallisuudesta.”

¹¹³ Gene Germanovich et al., “Enhancing US-Finnish and Regional Defence Cooperation: An Exploratory Analysis” (RAND Corporation, September 24, 2021), 10, https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RR1424-1.html.

¹¹⁴ Valtioneuvosto, “Government Report on Finnish Foreign and Security Policy.”

Government's term of office."¹¹⁵ The reports continue to only pay lip service to Finland's official policy of military non-alignment, with most security whitepapers only mentioning it once, and the 2016 Report on Finnish Foreign and Security Policy omitting it completely.¹¹⁶

NATO exercises reverted to a focus on territorial defense, no longer just participating in crisis management exercises. In addition to exercises held on Finnish soil, Finland began participating in joint Arctic Challenge Exercises starting in 2013. As mentioned before, in 2014, Finland joined NATO's Enhanced Opportunities Program, improving interoperability and integration with NATO forces. The program led Finland to participating in Arctic Challenge Exercises starting in 2014, providing deeper and tailor-made integration through regular consultations, enhanced access to interoperability programmes and exercises, information sharing, and closer association in times of crisis.¹¹⁷

PESCO, which was written into the EU Constitution through the Treaty of Lisbon in 2009, was finally activated in 2017. The majority of the EU member states agreed, including Finland.¹¹⁸ During this period, Finland voluntarily joined multiple projects, including the ambitious Military Mobility project which seeks to standardize military transport to allow for unfettered movement across EU borders.¹¹⁹ This is a clear change from the previous levels of inter-EU military coöperation, further integrating Finland with its European allies.

International coöperation

After the beginning of 2014, while the usual coöperation like with NATO and the EU grew in depth, Finland had a marked increase in collaborations bilaterally and regionally. A short list of agreements:

¹¹⁵ Valtioneuvosto, "Finnish Security and Defence Policy 2012."

¹¹⁶ Valtioneuvosto, "Government Report on Finnish Foreign and Security Policy."

¹¹⁷ NATO, "Partnership Interoperability Initiative" (NATO, March 7, 2024), https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topic_s_132726.htm.

¹¹⁸ European Union, "Council Decision (CFSP) 2017/2315 of 11 December 2017 Establishing Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) and Determining the List of Participating Member States," Council Decision 2017/2315 § (2017), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2017/2315/oj/eng>.

¹¹⁹ European Union, "Military Mobility (MM)" (Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), 2022), <https://www.pesco.europa.eu/project/military-mobility/>.

- Deepened defense coöperation with Sweden (2014)¹²⁰
- Arctic Coast Guard Forum (2015)
- Statement of Intent with the U.S. (2016)
- Framework Arrangement on Defence Cooperation with Estonia (2017)
- Joint Expeditionary Force led by the U.K (2017)
- Memorandum of Understanding with Sweden (2018)
- Framework Arrangement on Defence Cooperation with Norway (2018, 2021)
- European Intervention Initiative (2018)
- Finnish-Swedish-Norwegian trilateral Statement of Intent (2020)¹²¹

While previous periods had key expansions of coöperation like NATO's PfP or NORDEFECO, this period had a huge expansion of smaller, intertwining agreements. Many informal, smaller agreements from previous periods were now formalized and deepened.

Levels of Integration

Finland's level of openness was even greater during this period, demonstrated by how its tilt towards NATO and the West became even clearer. New agreements and memorandums were created, and old ones expanded. Within white papers, Finland began to directly name Russia as a challenge to Europe, saying that "Russia has mostly abandoned the cooperation-based security thinking. Rather, it now challenges the European security system."¹²² This is a drastic change from the careful wording of former white papers, ones that were careful not to directly call Russia a threat. However, Finnish policy continued to espouse non-alignment, even if in passing. In a written question (*kirjallinen kysymys*) to the parliament, Jussi Halla-aho asks whether the invasion of Crimea changes Finland's security calculus. Foreign Minister Erkki Tuomioja responds, "The Ukraine situation has created a serious crisis in Europe, but it does not yet constitute a threat to Finnish security."¹²³ Clearly while there was a new willingness to call Russia out, care in how and to what it was conducted was still there.

¹²⁰ Finnish Defence Forces and Swedish Armed Forces, "Final Reports on Deepened Defence Cooperation Between Finland and Sweden," May 6, 2014, <https://www.regeringen.se/globalassets/regeringen/dokument/forsvarsdepartementet/final-reports-on-deepened-defence-cooperation-between-finland-och-sweden.pdf>.

¹²¹ Germanovich et al., "Enhancing US-Finnish and Regional Defence Cooperation."

¹²² Valtioneuvosto, "Government Report on Finnish Foreign and Security Policy," 14.

¹²³ Tuomioja, "Venäjän asemaan ja uhkakuviin reagoiminen Suomessa," 3.

The range of nations and organizations that Finland was working with was as broad as ever, but more open. Informal agreements like with Sweden became formalized, and ties with other Nordics became deeper. As for wartime coöperation, Finland became increasingly involved in territorial defense exercises and not just focusing on crisis management. The activities, while explained as simply training for credible defense, began to take on what looked like collective defense practice.

Levels of screening

Along with the increased collaboration with Western organizations and countries came increasing ties and dependence. While Finland still had final say on any activities, it became further entangled in terms of military force, especially as its conscription numbers fell. The responsibility of establishing security has spread further out as Finland builds its capabilities on top of that of the EU, NATO, and other regional organizations. The Defence Forces alone are no longer sufficient in covering all the security needs, with international defense coöperation adding the extra deterrence needed.¹²⁴

Domestic circumstances

While NATO remained unpopular among the public, it grew as an object of discussion in the government. Questions were raised in parliament about how the Russian invasion of Crimea should change Finnish thinking, but the status quo was still maintained in official discussions on the topic.¹²⁵ In 2016, an assessment of NATO membership commissioned by the Ministry for Foreign Affairs was completed, demonstrating this change in orientation from years past. Ultimately even as consideration grew, no action was taken on the NATO question as accession was seen to simply provoke Russia further.¹²⁶ NATO latency continued to be the preferred situation.

¹²⁴ Valtioneuvosto, "Government's Defence Report," 16.

¹²⁵ Tuomioja, "Venäjän asemaan ja uhkakuviin reagoiminen Suomessa."

¹²⁶ Forsberg, "Four Rounds of the Finnish NATO Debate," 46.

Discussion

If we boil down the section above into ratings ranging from “Very Low” to “Very High” we can this table here.

Table 1: Period Ratings

Period	Credible Defense	Military non-alliance	International Coöperation	Integration	Screening
Cold War	Very high	Very High	Low	Low	High
1992–2007	High	High	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
2007–2014	High	High	Moderate-High	Moderate	Moderate
2014–2022	Very high	Moderate-High	High	Moderate-High	Low
Continuity	High	Moderate	Low	Low	Low

The table shows us that Finland’s adherence to its three-part security doctrine has varied over the past three decades. This conclusion is certainly not a surprise; many scholars have come to this same conclusion, such as Palosaari (2013), Pesu (2017), and Holmila and Ahonen (2022). What the chart does make clear is the gradual process in which Finland ramped up its integrative policy. While the underlying lesson of Finlandization continued to exist following the fall of the Soviet Union, its impact in Finland has continued to wane over the past 30 years.

If we look at Weislander’s (2022) criteria for evaluating continuity of policy, we see that Finland’s security doctrine is no longer a continuation of Cold War Finlandization, especially when compared to the post-Crimea status. An extension of a Finlandized policy would maintain Cold War-era values; something that we do not see in the chart. Thus, these new elements show that policy has shifted. Additionally, it matches Weislander’s assessment that a small state choosing to integrate would “conduct a policy with a high degree of integration and few elements of screening” with deterrence relying on that integration. This is precisely what we see with Finland: growing integration and decreasing screening.

The outward presentation that Finnish leaders present is one that attempts to maintain the status

quo, as seen in the incidents of self-censorship or kowtowing as Arter (2023) points out. So what explains the actual actions being taken behind the scenes? The slow build up with the West seemingly contradicts the displays of reluctance or self-censorship that Arter mentions. To understand this, these incidents must be placed in context to broader overarching steps of integration; this mixing of outward and inward action is actually consistent with historic Finnish foreign policy. This is a continuation of the Finnish balancing act: working behind the scenes to develop security and safety while maintaining relations as best as possible. This was practiced throughout all of the Cold War, understanding the realities of the situation with Russia, yet working to pursue its interests with the West as best as possible.¹²⁷

These findings line up exactly with Pesu's (2017) description of an "incremental divestment" of military non-alignment.¹²⁸ His report hit the nail exactly on the head. This kind of build up, integration, and coöperation explains why NATO accession came so quickly and easily for the country institutionally. All it needed was a shift in public opinion that came as a consequence of Russia's invasion in 2022. However, contrary to popular sentiment, this does not mean that Finlandization has ended within Finland. I argue that it has taken on a new form and will continue to shape both Finnish foreign and domestic policy into the future.

Finlandization's new meanings

As a reminder, Juntunen (2017) gives four different meanings for how the term "Finlandization" is used.

1. Descriptive: a neutral term to describe the voluntary relationship of a smaller power creating stability through reassuring a larger power with neutrality
2. Pejorative (international): *suomettuminen*, a larger power forcing a smaller one into neutrality
3. Pejorative (domestic): *suomettaminen*, a smaller power capitulating to a larger power to maintain sovereignty
4. Emancipatory: a smaller power taking initiative to neutralize the threat of a larger power without giving in (used by Soviet states in the 80s)

¹²⁷ Max Jakobson, "Substance and Appearance: Finland," *Foreign Affairs*, June 1, 1980, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/finland/1980-06-01/substance-and-appearance-finland>.

¹²⁸ Pesu, "What Non-Alignment?" 5.

I propose two additional ones:

1. A generalized one, one of warning
2. A generalized one, one of hope

With the recent accession into NATO, as well as the election of President Trump, Finland has been placed into another situation evocative of Cold War-era Finlandization. However, unlike how Finlandization is usually discussed, this way of thinking isn't directed at Russia, but rather informed by it and directed more broadly. This fear stems from Finland's history with Russia, a long-enduring fear of the loss of sovereignty and control.

Finland's independence was tenuous, only possible in a small opening of time during the October Revolution. This tenuous independence was threatened time and time again: during the interwar period, during WWII, throughout the Cold War, and even after with leaders like Vladimir Zhirinovskiy espousing a need to reclaim the 1900 imperial borders.¹²⁹ Over a hundred years, this created an internalized worry, one that Medvedev (1999) calls a "classical case of neurosis," one where Russia becomes the "subconsciousness" of Finland.¹³⁰ However, I argue that now with the accession to NATO, while the fear is no longer oriented specifically towards Russia, it persists in regards to any larger power in general.

We can see direct parallels between the Finnish perception of the USSR and the U.S. already in how the Finnish public has responded to President Alexander Stubb's past actions with President Trump. There is a current of discontent with how President Stubb is handling Finland's relationship with the U.S. An exemplary example of this is a political cartoon published in the *Helsingin Sanomat* by Ville Ranta. It depicts Stubb explaining the "three rules handling an unpredictable friend": in this case, the United States. The first rule is to not provoke, the second to listen to what the other has to say, and the last is to act accordingly. In the last step he is kneeling prostrate, with a man wearing a stereotypical Russian ushanka saying, "Hey. . . those are the old points!"

¹²⁹ Jacob W. Kipp, "The Zhirinovskiy Threat," *Foreign Affairs*, May 1, 1994, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/russia-fsu/1994-05-01/zhirinovskiy-threat>.

¹³⁰ Medvedev, "Russia as the Subconsciousness of Finland," 101.

Figure 2: Political cartoon by Ville Ranta (2025)

As shown in this comic, to Finns these actions evoke a memory of Finlandization vis-à-vis the USSR. However, in this case, its directed towards the U.S.. This particular detail is not something I've seen in existing research regarding Finlandization: a reorientation and generalization of the lessons learned.

Stubb's recent trip to play golf with Trump was treated in a similar manner, with concern being raised that Stubb is only playing too much into the U.S.'s interests and not pushing for Finland's as strongly.¹³¹ Although President Stubb being seated next to President Trump at Pope Francis's funeral was a coincidence based on alphabetical country names, it just added to the discussion of Finland and the U.S. being drawn closer.

When talking publically, President Stubb is always careful to treat American interests with nuance and care. In an interview with Christiane Amanpour, President Stubb said in regards to his

¹³¹ Tommi Nieminen, "Tie Mar-a-Lagoon" (Helsingin Sanomat, April 4, 2025), <https://www.hs.fi/feature/art-2000011136218.html>; YLE News, "After Golfing with Stubb, Trump Says US Will 'Purchase Badly Needed Icebreakers' from Finland" (Yle Uutiset, March 30, 2025), <https://yle.fi/a/74-20152664>.

golf trip with Trump:

“I do say one thing though, there is nothing so far that I have heard from the President or the President’s administration or people around him which would sort of reduce the commitment of the United States to NATO. Quite the contrary, the Americans are pushing the Europeans and the other allies to take more responsibility, and I think the Americans are right for doing it.”¹³²

Stubb has made this point previously about Europe needing to take responsibility, but he never mentions the way in which the U.S. has been pushing for this change. His publicly expressed views are always the most charitable way of viewing American actions, views that his other European counterparts have not adopted in the same way.¹³³ There’s no denying that the visuals of how the U.S. is being treated are similar to that of Finlandization. There’s appeasement, a concerted effort of closeness, and an avoidance of critique: the U.S. is Finland’s next USSR. Not in that the U.S. threatens Finland, but that Finland will differ and appease the U.S.

Continuing into the future, this lesson of Finlandization will play a role in Finnish policymaking in this new, generalized form. The realist policy conducted by the political elite exists so that Finland can continue toe the line between provocation and sedation. With Stubb, it is in an attempt to maintain positive relations with the U.S. and try to ensure American commitment to Europe and to NATO, which Finland only just recently joined. The issue is that it comes into conflict with the wider public fear of giving up sovereignty and control: the lesson learned from the USSR.

Some might argue that this perception is simply a response to the Ukraine War, that citizens don’t want a weak leader in these times, or a response to Trump fatigue pervasive in much of the world. However, this kind of Finlandization is by no means new. The fear of capitulating power and sovereignty to a non-Russian power first appeared with Finland’s accession into the EU. That discourse took the same form, a worry of giving of sovereignty, losing control to greater powers, and becoming non-neutral. This is seen in a *kirjallinen kysymys* (“written question”) by MP

¹³² Christiane Amanpour, “Finnish President Alexander Stubb On Trump’s Approach to Russia and Ukraine,” May 9, 2025, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hdsIL-sQUVY>.

¹³³ Ivo H. Daalder, “NATO Without America,” *Foreign Affairs*, March 28, 2025, <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/united-states/nato-without-america>.

Sulo Aittooniemi to parliament, asking how EU accession is compatible with Finnish neutrality.¹³⁴ To assuage wider concerns that Finland is giving up its decision-making capabilities, the Finnish Government published a 1995 white paper, which as Blank (1996) explains, expressly commits to a maintenance of independent defense.¹³⁵ This even comes up occasionally nowadays about NATO, worried that being a single nation in a large alliance will limit Finland's influence and thus decision-making ability.¹³⁶ While it can also be seen as a natural action by a small state, this concern is rooted more deeply in the Finnish subconscious, as explained above. The two conflicting perspectives will continue to butt heads as the political elite attempt to secure aid and commitment from the U.S., while the public continues to express its discontent and fear that Finland is giving up control or being too appeasing.

The second use/definition that I suggest is the topic of the third chapter, a usage that reduces the term and highlights the positive outcomes from the Soviet era of Finlandization.

¹³⁴ Väyrynen, "Euroopan unionin jäsenyyden vaikutuksista Suomen ulko- ja puolustuspolitiikkaan."

¹³⁵ Stephen J. Blank, "Finnish Security and European Security Policy" (Strategic Studies Institute, US Army War College, 1996), v, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep11400>.

¹³⁶ Matti Pesu and Tuomas Iso-Markku, "Finland as a NATO Ally: First Insights into Finnish Alliance Policy," *Finnish Foreign Policy Papers*, December 15, 2022, 16, <https://fia.fi/en/publication/finland-as-a-nato-ally>.

Chapter 3: Finlandization as an Export

With the ongoing conflict in Ukraine, political officials across the world have been attempting to come up with a solution. For some, the solution is applying the “Finnish model”, i.e. Finlandization. Most recently, it was Former Chancellor of Germany Olaf Scholz, who opined in 2024 that Ukraine should become Finlandized instead of seeking NATO membership.¹³⁷ This suggestion is by no means new, nor exclusive to Ukraine. As discussed in *Finlandization as a Framework*, references to the Finnish “model” have been made since the Cold War with the example that Juntunen (2017) provides being Soviet states during the 80s. Since then, Finlandization has been applied to Taiwan, Mongolia, Georgia, and others.

However, this suggestion is consistently decried by Finns as reductive, harmful, and unproductive. Still to this day, most Finns view the Finlandized period as a period of at-worst dictatorship, at-best a necessary evil.¹³⁸ To suggest another country take the same route is unthinkable.

Juntunen (2017) explains the application as “based on an overgeneralised historical lesson that relies on a mythological re-appropriation of the original process of Finlandization during the Cold War”.¹³⁹ Finlandization is being reduced from a highly contextual phenomenon to one that proponents of the “model” mythologize into a solution for any nation struggling with a domineering neighbor. Those on the outside shift the term from a negative one, to a positive.

Finlandization is not the only, nor even most famous, historical “model” that has been analogized into the present. It is part of the IR realist tradition to draw lessons from past events, for in their view, international relation is a fixed game of power politics. If something worked for a small state in the past, then something *must* be able to be drawn from it. Finland, a small nation, an anomaly, managed to, in a way, defeat the Soviet Union and become a flourishing state. But alas that is what Finland did: be an anomaly.

¹³⁷ Eldar Mamedov, “Western Leader Blurts Out What Was Once Taboo on Ukraine” (Responsible Statecraft, November 8, 2024), <https://responsiblestatecraft.org/germany-ukraine-2669632533/>.

¹³⁸ Mahtlahti, “How Do Older/Younger Generations Perceive Kekkonen? How Is He Portrayed in Public Schools? A Great Leader? A Good Leader with Some Negative Attributes? A Necessary Evil? A Terrible Authoritarian One? How Is He Portrayed in the Media/Movies/TV Series (If Any)?” Reddit Post (r/Finland, May 29, 2020), https://www.reddit.com/r/Finland/comments/gsm8pf/how_do_olderyounger_generations_perceive_kekkonen/.

¹³⁹ Juntunen, “Helsinki Syndrome,” 17.

The failure of comparison

The application of the model of Finlandization is predicated on its divorce from the historical context. To outsiders, all that is seen of Finlandization is a small state somehow managing to survive a tense period against an overbearing neighbor. This, however, fails to take into account any of the unique or nuanced context that sets the “Finnish model” apart.

As outlined in the *Literature Review*, much work has already been done on the downsides of Finlandization: the reduction in sovereignty, the compromises in democracy, the widespread self-censorship. Some have also pointed out differentiating factors in the Finnish context: an expectation that the other side won’t attack, completely lacking external alliances, and a complete tolerance for self-defense capacity building.¹⁴⁰ But one factor that I don’t see as often that is critical in allowing Finlandization to function is the role of then President Urho Kekkonen.

It was widely understood by both the Finnish public and Soviet leadership that the somewhat secure relationship could only function with Kekkonen at the helm. Kekkonen leveraged his relationship with the USSR in what Lavery describes as “playing the Moscow card.”¹⁴¹ He asserted that he was the only one that could maintain trust with the Soviets and the Soviets echoed that claim. Over time, parties that wanted success had to follow Kekkonen’s lead or come under the scrutiny of or even outright dismissal by the USSR (as was the case with the Note Crisis in 1961 where Soviet pressures led to Kekkonen dissolving the dissatisfactory parliament.) Kekkonen thus solidified his rule as President for 26 years thanks to this relationship with the USSR, only ending as his health worsened. Kekkonen played a crucial role in establishing a stable working relationship between Finland and the Soviet Union. Without his ability to garner personal trust with and reassure Khrushchev of Finnish neutrality, both the USSR and the West could have seen Finland very differently. Without the stability provided by Kekkonen’s political maneuvering, Finland may have been seen as too risky for the interests for both the West and East, leading to a worse outcome. There is no such parallel in either the Ukraine nor the Taiwan case.

¹⁴⁰ Kallio, “Finlandization Is No Model for Taiwan to Follow”; Lavery, “Finlandization Interview.”

¹⁴¹ Lavery, “Finlandization Interview.”

The last time that Finlandization was applicable as a model was perhaps during the Cold War, within other Soviet Bloc nations. Juntunen (2017) explores this in his fourth definition of Finlandization, one that is emancipatory. Ultimately, the interest in Finland boiled down to its ability to “maintain flexible relations with the West without provoking harsh Soviet sanctions.”¹⁴² It is here that Finlandization’s unique context applied the most and could be argued for in that sense. Finland was a nation under the umbrella of the USSR, but one that aspired for Western integration. This appealed to democratic opposition movements in Poland and Hungary, who used Finlandization as a source of inspiration.¹⁴³ But even here there are differences in situations; Finland’s relationship with the USSR was just too different from that of states actually part of the Warsaw Pact that that fact alone would color any analysis of applicability. There will always be lines to draw between comparisons, and as shown above, they are legitimate lines that may preclude any transference of lessons. Finlandization is not simply a means of appeasement and neutrality. Its a complicated and distinct phenomenon that arose due to decades of conflict, and a unique political situation.

The reductionism of realism in applying models

The IR theory of realism predicts that international conflict is predictable and understandable through the lens of great power politics. It is within this framework that small states are obligated to act in whatever way would allow for their survival. The realist interpretation of Finlandization in this case takes on the view that this was a natural response by Finland. Finland naturally acquiesced to Russia in order to preserve its sovereignty.

By all scholarly accounts, Finlandization was absolutely a realist policy, a response to a threatening state. However, the application of Finlandization now fails to recognize what the *actual* realist observations were by Finland during the Cold War:

1. Finland was under a consistent threat, a credible threat of overthrow from Russia.
2. Finland believed itself to have no allies, to be completely alone.

¹⁴² Juntunen, “Helsinki Syndrome,” 69.

¹⁴³ Juntunen, 68.

Because of these specific factors, its only option was to acquiesce to Russia through the empowerment of President Kekkonen.

However, if we compare these two points to the positions that Ukraine and Taiwan are in, we find that in neither situation the aforementioned points are true. Ukraine is actively undergoing an invasion and has the expressed support of many Western countries. Taiwan may have a credible threat of invasion from China, but continues to have active allies in the U.S., Japan, Australia, and others. Even just using a realist lens, the application of Finlandization here does not line up with the realist understanding of the situation in post-WWII Finland. The realist usage of Finlandization as a model fails to understand the realist factors vis-à-vis Finland and the USSR that drove such a response.

The question as to why politicians and political scientists are so eager to use the Finnish model is more difficult. I believe that it's a misinterpretation of the historical situation, boiling down these factors to simply "small nation, large neighbor" and calling it a day. That is not even to even to mention any deeper historical relationship or domestic factors that color the development of the two factors. Juntunen's (2017) paper on this explains that it is this complexity that "*increase[s]* its performative efficacy: it is a concept that carries multiple interpretations and imaginaries within it, thus having plenty of rhetorical potential without clear strategic accuracy." And we see this with how many definitions that it's had in the past, and the new definitions that I've given it in *Chapter 2: Finlandization as a Continuation of History*; Finland's unique success together with the complexity of Finlandization prime it to be used and applied out of location and context.

What model to follow then?

So if Cold War-era Finlandization is not a model to follow, then what should be? The overarching issue here is that the focus for external viewers is always the Cold War period. Lessons on how to deal with *current-day Russia* are always drawn from interactions with its *predecessor* during the Cold War. This fails to recognize differences between the two nations and the explicit changes in relationship between Finland and its eastern neighbor before and after 1992. If anything, modern

models should follow how countries have dealt with Russia *following* the end of the Cold War.

Ålander (2024) comes to this conclusion as well, arguing that the Finnish integration over the past three decades following the Cold War demonstrates that a shift in geopolitical attitudes is possible.¹⁴⁴ Surprisingly, she is the only person I've seen in my research that has come to this conclusion explicitly, an article I found only after searching to see if someone has brought this up before. Most other critiques of Finlandization as a model end up with an outright rejection with no suggestion of what could be learned from Finland, like that of Kallio (2010); few draw lessons from broader themes of Finlandization, like Holmila and Ahonen (2022).

I argue that Finland's actions following the fall of the Soviet Union is an applicable model for other nations. We can see that this "post-Finlandized" model is characterized by a buildup of Westward political and military integration, but *always* with reassurance and a consideration of Russian interests and fears. It was in this slow process that Finland was able to pursue its long-term goal of security through Western integration. Unlike Finlandization, the post-Finlandization model doesn't operate with a dictator in mind, nor with the harsh downsides of giving up sovereignty and control. While certainly in the beginning post-Finlandization, as Arter (2023) explains, Finland had a naïve belief that Russia would democratize; we can see through the different phases that this threat eventually turned Finnish policy around, allowing for a build-up of security assurances and military capability. It wasn't until Russia proved itself to be an overt military threat with its invasion of Ukraine in 2022 that the post-Finlandized paradigm needed to be changed.¹⁴⁵ However, by then, Finland had undertaken enough integration with organizations like the EU and NATO that breaking its formal non-militarily aligned policy was not difficult.

Unlike Ålander however, who argues that the solution for Ukraine could be found now, I believe it's too early (or late, depending on how you frame it) to find a solution for Ukraine now through a look at Finland's slow integration. The lessons drawn from Finland's actions discussed in *Applying*

¹⁴⁴ Minna Ålander, "Why Finland Thinks Finlandization Is a Bad Idea for Ukraine" (Atlantic Council, December 13, 2024), <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/ukrainealert/why-finland-thinks-finlandization-is-a-bad-idea-for-ukraine/>.

¹⁴⁵ As for why the 2013 invasion of Crimea did not activate this concern is a separate issue, but can be boiled down to the lack of public concern.

the Framework require a relatively stable situation between states; clearly not the case for Ukraine now. Perhaps once the situation stabilizes, if it ever does, then some kind of cautious integration policy could be pursued, but certainly not now. While it may be the wrong time for Ukraine to follow the “post-Finlandization” model, other countries may be able to learn from it.

Finland’s actions show the capacity for a state in a constrained situation to build towards an eventual security guarantee. Plenty of research has gone into how Finland did this, such as Pesu’s (2017) paper outlining the post-Crimea shift. What hasn’t been researched is the possibility of this being applied elsewhere. While I think its out of the scope of this one year master’s thesis, the development of “post-Finlandization” as a model would be an interesting topic of research in the future. Over the past three decades, Finland has radically shifted in its approach to security, a process that can certainly provide guidance for other nations. The post-Cold War context is certainly a better model than Finlandization of yore, but it is to be seen if Finland’s unique history will foil any attempts at external application yet again.

Annexes

List of Terms

Collective security: An arrangement between states where an attack on one is an attack on all, necessitating a collective response.

Constructivism: An *IR* theory emphasizing the role of ideas, norms, and social constructs in shaping the behavior and identities of states, rather than material forces like power or economics.

FCMA Treaty: The Agreement of Friendship, Cooperation, and Mutual Assistance of 1948 between Finland and the Soviet Union. It recognized Finland's independence, but obligated it to resist attacks by the West, and not attack the USSR. It necessitated Finnish neutrality to function. The treaty ended with the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1992. Also known as the *YYA Treaty*.

Finlandization: Known as *suomettuminen* (or less commonly *suomettaminen*), this is the neutral policy that Finland took during the Cold-War due to its history and relationship to the Soviet Union. This policy affected both foreign and domestic politics.

Historicism: A theory that emphasizes the importance of historical context in understanding events, ideas, or social phenomena, asserting that these cannot be understood without it.

Integrational policy: A policy that grows a nation's connections with and cooperation with another body, bringing them closer and becoming more similar.

IR: International relations.

Liberalism: An *IR* theory that highlights the importance of institutions, cooperation, trade, and the promotion of democracy to achieve peace and prosperity among states. It rejects the power politics focus of *realism*.

Military non-alliance: A policy of not signing a *collective security* agreement or military alliances, maintaining independence in defense and security decisions.

Neo-classical realism: An *IR* theory combining classical realism's focus on human nature and domestic politics with neorealism's emphasis on power politics in the international system.

Neutrality: A policy of remaining impartial and not taking sides in conflicts or alliances, aiming to

avoid entanglement in wars or disputes between other states.

Post-Finlandization: The continuation of *Finlandization* into the post-Cold War era.

Realism: An *IR* theory focusing on states' pursuit of power, security, and survival in an anarchic international system, driven by self-interest and competition.

YYA Treaty: *Ystävyys-, yhteistyö- ja avunantosopimus (YYA-sopimus)*. See *FCMA Treaty*.

Finlandization: Interview with Jason Lavery

Interviewer: AnThu Nguyen, University of California, Berkeley

Interviewee: Professor Jason Lavery, Oklahoma State University

Location: Zoom

Date: December 13th, 2024

Duration: 01:54:26

Nguyen: First thing, if you don't mind, could you introduce your name and title?

Lavery: I am Jason Lavery. L A V E R Y my last name. I'm regents professor at Oklahoma State University and the title Regents professor is given to, we don't really have endowed chairs here. So it's given to professors who are, it's a recognition of research excellence or productivity. So it's like you become full professor and then about 10 percent of full professors get this title. I am also an adjunct professor, permanent adjunct professor or docent. Finnish title, *docentti*. I'm a docent of the church history of Finland and Scandinavia at Helsinki University. And so those are my two major titles.

Nguyen: Okay, great. I guess I'll start off with a broader question. What is Finlandization and how would you define it?

Lavery: I would, the definition I use this in my history of Finland book. I use the definition that was developed by the historian Jukka Tarkka, who said that Finlandization is a domestic policy through foreign policy. And so it's a, everything for foreign policy is used as. Foreign policy imperatives or challenges are used to drive domestic policy.

This is different than, how traditionally, especially in the Cold War era, Finlandization was defined. I think ultimately that the real kind of story about Finlandization and Finnish-Soviet relations is how it was used domestically. And that's where a lot of the discussion comes from when you talk about, politicians being, too deferential to Russia or the Soviet Union, or using the Russian threat as a, domestic policy thing.

So that's how I define it is an excessive use of foreign policy. It's domestic policy conducted by foreign policy, and that is the kind of the excessive use of foreign policy aspects to drive domestic

policy. So that's how I would that's how I define it as, as briefly as I can.

Nguyen: Are there any things that we need to keep in mind when discussing Finlandization? Anything that people assume or get wrong?

Lavery: I think there are a lot of things that different things have been gotten wrong at different times. The, during the Cold War era the idea that the Soviet Union you know, that somehow Finland was less of a democracy. Or less of a market economy than other European countries.

That was something, the West got wrong. You had, multi party democracy you had, free elections, the Soviet influence was created by domestic elites and the broadly by the people. Who approved a lot of this. There, there wasn't any, and there were many aspects of Finnish-Soviet relations that did a lot of good things for Finland that people liked. So it wasn't this yes, the Soviets had, people they did a lot of cultivating of politicians and so forth. But the idea that Finland wasn't a democracy is wrong and the limitations on Finland's democracy that happened during the Cold War were, largely choices Finns themselves made.

And if they hadn't made those choices, there would still be, relations with the Soviet Union. That's the other thing. And Finland had a market economy. Yeah, and even though there were for much of the Cold War era there, there were communists in the government and as well as a social democratic party that was in more of the governments, but there's a strong sense of private property, private ownership, private entrepreneurship in Finland that reaches even into the left.

One of the things about the end of the Cold War and which caused this part of the reasons why it caused there was an economic depression in Finland with the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Finnish Communist Party went into bankruptcy. Everybody went into bankruptcy, even the communists who you don't associate with a capitalist economy or anything.

That's one thing. When we look at the post Cold War period, And people looking back on that period is that one thing is that the Finnish policy of deference, of strong deference to the Soviet Union and this recognition that Finland was a part of this.

When World War II ended, Finland became a part of the Soviet Union's political and military sphere of influence. This was something that people across the board in Finland understood and

agreed to. The foreign policy that Finland had toward the Soviet Union of recognizing Finland's new place in Europe was something that was, recognized and supported by politicians from, the right to the far left.

J. K. Paasikivi could be, as Finland's first, post war prime minister, was a member of the conservative party. So even though conservatives weren't represented formally in the government, it was people from him on the right all the way across the political spectrum realized that as of fall of 1944, there really wasn't any other option, there was no party, there was no country that was going to come and save Finland via the Soviet Union, Germany was heading to defeat, the Soviet Union's allies, Finland's fellow democracies weren't going to come to help because they were a part of this kind of carving up of Europe into spheres of influence and so they weren't going to argue with the Soviets, that the Soviets wanted Finland recognized as part of a sphere of influence because then, the Soviets could complain about why don't we have some, share in Italy, for example, parts of the parts of Europe that were, defeated or liberated tended to be part of that victorious power sphere influence.

But no one was going to come and help Finland. So the only thing that Finland could do in that situation was. Look for the best deal possible with the Soviet Union. So that's one thing that people don't get is that people would whine about Finland being, deferential. Where were you guys to help?

And, they weren't. And you could say there were other neutral countries in the Cold War period, like neighboring Sweden or Austria, that, that were less, deferential to the Soviet Union, but those countries didn't share a land border with the Soviet Union.

Those countries were also had, Sweden, not so much Austria but Sweden, was in the Cold War period, had secret ties with NATO and Sweden was developing, a lot of people don't know that Sweden in the fifties was developing a nuclear bomb. Yeah.

'Cause Sweden had this large nuclear power industry and they were thinking of building a nuclear bomb to defend themselves. There were a lot of countries, like of Sweden's size, that were thinking about this after World War II. But no, Sweden was seriously considering it.

So those countries aren't to be compared with Finland because of either their geography their proximity or potential military power. I think that's another thing that people don't get, they need to

go back to the fall of 1944. The the other thing is that, this was a foreign policy that, yes, deferred to the Soviet Union in order for Finland to maintain its, democracy and market institutions and open society, but it was also a policy that, it's hard to explain this, but, Finland's foreign policy did in some respects develop from a position of strength.

If you look at the Soviet Union's aim and respect to Finland during the wars of World War II was to conquer the country. The Soviet Union did not get that. So the Soviets had to themselves had to recognize an independent Finland that they could not dominate.

So the relationship was also a concession on the part of the Soviets. That they would have to accept this, and this goes to another point about the relationship is that the Soviets accepted it not only because of Finnish military sacrifices but also because the Soviet Union in Russia, even today is primarily a defensive interest in Finland, Finland cannot be used to attack other countries really. This is a different from let's say Poland or East Germany or Czechoslovakia where you could really use those countries to expand westward. This is one of the reasons why there's so much concern about Ukraine because, the idea is Putin gets Ukraine, he can then turn to Poland or other countries.

So I think to summarize you, you don't have the situation as it existed in 1944 for both sides. And also, Finland's geographical position meant for the Soviets it was primarily a defensive asset rather than an offensive asset. And also, as I said this was a foreign policy that even though there were, especially in the Kekkonen era, a lot of abuses the foreign policy was abused for domestic reasons, hence Finlandization.

And this is what a lot of critics of the excessive use of a foreign policy and domestic policy people said is that anybody who ran Finland after World War Two would have had a policy of constructive deference or constructive appeasement to the Soviet Union because it was the only way, but it was also a way that benefited the country in many ways.

So I hope that gets to your, what you were trying to get at. When I talk with students with Finnish students about this in my classes people tend to forget how beneficial Finnish-Soviet trade was. They also don't understand that the relation over time, by the 1970s, Finland's relationship with the Soviet Union gave it a special kind of mission.

Helsinki was a place where American and Soviet leaders met. You have the OSCE conference in 1975 with, that Kekkonen was able to pull off. Finland developed for itself a secure position in Europe that it did not have before World War II. And so when a lot of the discussion happens about how the country was so supine via the Soviet Union a lot of the baby gets thrown out with the bathwater.

Anyway, I hope that answers your question.

Nguyen: Definitely, yeah. So you talked about it a little bit, that we need to when we're talking about Finlandization and its effects, we need to contextualize it in the situation as it was in 1944. Could you tell me a little bit more about what that situation was? What was the relationship between Finland and the Soviet Union? What happened?

Lavery: The countries have been at war since if you want to put it in the narrowest sense, it's 1941, but really since 1939. There's the Winter War, 39 to 40. The two countries sign a peace treaty, but really no peace occurs. The Soviets still have made many menacing maneuvers toward Finland.

Finland, for its part starts cultivating Germany as a potential ally, and it creates this vicious cycle where Finland turns to Germany, the Soviets are aggressive toward Finland, Finland turns to Germany. The Soviets then increase the threatening behavior. In 1941, Finland joins Germany in its invasion of the Soviet Union.

After the defeat of Stalingrad, 1943, Finland then decided it needed to get out of the war. Germany was not going to win the war. There's a series of attempts to achieve a separate peace with the Soviet Union, which the Germans are able to put the kibosh on several times, but the Finns keep popping up.

In the summer of 1944, specifically in June, 1944, the German siege of Leningrad is broken by the Soviets. So the Soviets by the spring of 1944 are on the Karelian Isthmus. And by June they've moved up quite a bit and Finns are in retreat. The Finns start trying to open up real negotiations again with the Soviet Union. The Germans catch this and they threaten Finland. They begin to stop sending Finland food and weapons. And what the Soviets want is a no separate peace agreement with Finland. The Finns will agree not to have a separate peace with the Soviet. They'll go down

together if they go down. The Finns say the president of Finland at that time, Risto Ryti, said, if the Soviets wanted a formal state treaty, it would be ratified by parliament. And, Ryti said it's got this war going on. Parliament's got a lot to do and so forth. So how about I just make you my personal promise that as long as I'm president of the Republic of Finland, there will be no separate peace between Finland and the Soviet Union. The Germans say, great, they get the presidents on board, the weapons start coming in.

And so the front stabilizes in July, 1944, but the front stabilized the Finns open up again and the Soviets agree to have negotiations. And so the president of Finland resigns. He says that this was the whole thing, the agreement was only between him and basically between him and Adolf Hitler. It wasn't anybody else. I think it's just one of these really, just really, cutting political moments. It's as I say to my class is always like the "na-na-na-na-na" of the war for Finland because the president resigns. Nobody else was bound by this agreement. So the new government comes in.

Marshal Mannerheim becomes president. The Finns were knew that time was of the essence, but also they knew that the Soviets did not want unconditional surrender, which had been what the allies had demanded of all countries fighting with Nazi Germany but ultimately didn't happen in like in Italy, it didn't happen and Mussolini was overthrown, but a new government comes in. The Finns know they can get an agreement short of unconditional surrender to the Soviets.

The Finns also know that for the Soviets, getting to Berlin is more important than getting to Helsinki cause there's now among the allies this rush to get to Germany to set up their positions for the post war order. In September 1944, an armistice agreement is reached by which the most important, biggest thing is Finland gives up territory so the current borders of Finland and Russia are formed by that.

Finland also had to agree to lease a naval base at Porkkala it's about 20, 25 miles from downtown Helsinki. If you've ever been to Espoo, Espoo's Eastern neighbor is Helsinki. Espoo's Western neighbor is Kirkkonummi, which Porkkala is a part. So that's how close it was to, but they set up a naval base there.

War reparations, Finland had to pay war reparations. There was also a series of organizations

that the Soviets wanted banned, what they called fascist and Hitlerite organizations. And Finland also had to agree to remove German troops from its soil. So that was the peace treaty, but there was no particular Soviet demand on what the government should look like. And part of that might be because you had people like J. K. Paasikivi, he'd be involved in the peace settlement. You had Mannerheim's foreign minister, Carl Enckell was known as an old Russian hand. So they put in people who the Soviets knew and had dealt with in the past. Maybe not with great results, but they were people that didn't make the Soviets just flinch, like we're not going to talk to these guys at all. But that's the situation Finland had to, cede territory, had to evacuate its population that lived there. Everybody left had 10 days to leave and then Finland had to yet had to turn around and declare war on Germany and evict the German troops from Northern Finland.

So that's the situation. And the Soviets did not get a conquest of Finland but they got a government that was willing to work with it and the Soviets had tried for six years to conquer the country, realizing that it's not going to work. The war is coming to an end. We'll take our winnings and leave and the winnings were what they basically needed to prevent putting Finland in the hands of a foreign adversary. The Allies recognized that Finland was a part of the Soviet sphere of influence.

So they got basically what they needed, not necessarily what they wanted, to quote the old, Rolling Stones song. And so they walked away. So that was the situation as of the fall of 1944. And then by April 1945, German troops are out of the country and, there's peace.

Nguyen: With that established, following World War II, was Finlandization just informed by their experience with these wars? Was it informed by the realities of the situation of a potential invasion or threat from the Soviet Union, or was it something deeper as well? Something more historical having been under Russian control for what was it, over a hundred years?

Lavery: I would say it's all three. There's a strong sense, especially in the Cold War era, a strong sense that the policy that was pursued toward the Soviet Union after World War II was the best way to respect the sacrifices made. That the people who had fought and died, put the country in a position where it could maintain a free order inside the country. So the immediate outcome of

the war and then the immediate sacrifice certainly informed this policy in addition to the fact that everybody realized again that nobody was going to come and help Finland at this moment. We have to get the best deal we can.

To go back longer, Finland had since becoming independent in 1917 had searched for a solution that would neutralize the Soviet Union. This is the more medium term thing. I think you're asking about in terms of how people were informed there's the immediate outcome of the war, but there's this whole journey of Finland as an independent state that sought to find some solution that would neutralize as they put it "the Soviet threat." So Finland turns to other countries that bordered the Soviet Union, the so called "border state policy" in the 1920s. They want to a military arrangement with those countries. That doesn't work in large part because the countries couldn't decide which country was, over the long term, the bigger threat, Germany or the Soviet Union. For a country like Poland, they're looking both ways while, the Baltic states and Finland are looking more toward the Soviet Union.

But they went to there. Finland tried to find a collective security solution through the League of Nations. And then in the late thirties, they turned to their Scandinavian neighbors. And there too, you had the same problem as in the border state policy. The countries couldn't agree on which country, Germany or the Soviet Union, was the bigger threat.

And then the winter war starts, Finland fights largely alone. Then they align themselves with Germany, all of these attempts to find a collective security or put Finland in a larger collective security solution didn't work. Finland was not only alone in the fall of 1944. If people look back on it, people after the war would look back on it, Finland was basically alone since 1917 via the Soviet Union. That kind of, informs people as well. And then, Finland is a part of the Russian empire. We talked about this a bit last time, is that you have these two schools of thought that develop on how to deal with Russia.

One is this constitutionalist legalist don't give them an inch line, and then the appeasement line in which, I try to look at it as constructive appeasement because the people who approved of this line didn't see it as giving the Soviets everything. But this idea of constructive appeasement that if you

recognize the Soviet security interests in respect of Finland, if you respect the fact and understand that the Soviet Union sees Finland in defensive terms, the Soviets will leave Finland largely alone and, most of the 108 years Finland was a part of the Russian Empire that actually happened. Even in terms of the period since the late 90s until independence, when there was an attempt to unify Finland more with the rest of the Russian Empire, there was still a lot that the Russians didn't seek to touch. Somebody like J. K. Paasikiviki, who was a supporter of this constructive appeasement line, was one of the founding fathers of it from the 1890s and he's still around in 1944. For people like him, that was a really important experience of what was the 19th century and so it was informed by all on all three levels of these historical events.

Nguyen: Okay. So you explained the constructive appeasement stance. What was the constitutionalists' argument or position?

Lavery: Basically the difference between the two has to do with the role of the Finnish state. In, in 1809 or 1808, when Finland became a part of the Russian Empire, Emperor Alexander set up separate Finnish state institutions because he had promised the people of Finland, in a way to pacify Finland, so Finland would not be a problem while Alexander was focusing more on Central Europe and eventually fighting Napoleon, again, you see kind of Central Europe's more important than Finland, just to pacify the Finns and prevent any rebellion, he said he was going to respect Finland's laws, the position of the Lutheran Church in the country, as well as the privileges of the various estate groups. To do that, you needed a whole new, you couldn't just have Russian institutions maintain the status quo in Finland, because they didn't fit. Russia was under a totally different legal system. And Alexander said that the Finns could keep the old Swedish legal traditions. So in order to maintain that, you have to set up separate institutions for Finland that will maintain the laws and maintain the status quo run by, these are extensions of the emperor's power, Finland's not a democracy or anything, but he needs to set up different bodies in order to keep these pledges that he made. So he does this. Now what happens is when problems start happening in the 90s and the Russians start saying we want to reduce the scope of the separate Finnish state institutions and bring Finland more into the purview of Russian imperial institutions, the constitutionalists say that if you

reduce the Finnish state, and you allow the Russians to govern Finland more like it is a province or a region of Russian Empire, it will ultimately mean the end of Finnish culture, the Finnish language, for which many Constitutionalists had fought for and it would also end the idea of a Finnish nation, even if it's inside the Russian Empire. So for the constitutionalist, state and nation were the same.

The Constitutionalists also argued that the promises that Alexander made, a deal's a deal. When they didn't quite get that, yeah, Alexander made those promises, but he was also an absolute ruler. And it was just something that the estates that met with Alexander in 1809 agreed with. So Alexander could change the terms of the agreement. So that's why you can't give the Russians an inch on anything, because if you give them an inch, it will mean the end of the Finnish nation. What the constructive appeasement crowd argued was that first off, Russia is the stronger part partner here, so they can change things. They have great latitude in changing things in a way that the Finnish side can't stop. And if you concede to the Russians their security interests, that is, if you concede to the Russians who in the 1890s wanted to reduce Finland's state institutions and legal system, make it more Russian. Conceding that to the Russians means conceding their security concerns. They believed that if you made those concessions, the Russians would leave Finland's culture and sense of nationhood, of Finnishness and language, alone. And so for the appeasement people, state and nation were not necessarily linked for the constitutionalists they were.

And so it goes back to those differences. And actually, the constitutionalists had points because you could see how reducing state institutions might mean a reduction because so much of Finland as a separate nation came about as a result of the creation of these separate institutions, there wasn't an idea of a Finnish nation when Finland was a part of the Swedish kingdom. You have these state institutions created and Finns start thinking, "We are separate. We are a people, we are a nation." So there's a logic in the constitutionalists, the state, the creation of a state helped create a nation.

If you get rid of the state, the future of the nation is threatened. Yeah, there is a sense of a Finland and Finns, when Finland is a part of the Swedish kingdom, a regional, like being a Southerner in the United States, people know what it is, but there's not really a boundary to it.

And there's no political institutions, there are other Southern states, but there's not a state of

Southern in the US if that makes any sense. But, during the late 1890s, when the Russians started this pure process of imperializing Finland's institutions, actually the use of Finnish as a language in government increases. And there are measures the Russians take that actually help with, and this is something the Russians had been doing, for decades, fostering the use of the Finnish language was something the Russians continued to do not because they were, touchy feely, multicultural kind of, cultural woke people or anything, it was because they were still, by 20th century, incredibly paranoid of Finland separating from the Russian empire and rejoining Sweden. They supported Finnish in order to, weaken the use of Swedish as the language of the elite, so those were the tubes.

In some respects, both, at least what I see, both schools had their strength. And I think that's part of the reason why you still see these two approaches to Russia. They would play out even when Finland became independent because they both go to the real heart of some important aspects of not only Finland, but of Russia as well.

Nguyen: Okay, so I guess, would you agree to the statement or disagree to the statement that Finlandization as it was during the Cold War was a realist policy. Because you said that it took in parts of the situation at the time as well as the historical aspect.

Lavery: I would say, yes, it is a realistic policy. That is in terms of how to deal with the Soviet Union. Yes, it's a policy of realism. And at the time people said that, this is just, it's realism. And in that sense it was, I would say maybe, good realism.

The problem is how it was used domestically. People would try to be in domestic politics, especially, this really happens in the Kekkonen era. You don't see much of this in the Paasikivi presidency or the Paasikivi prime minister.

So basically 1944 to 56, if you put prime minister and president together, but in the Kekkonen era, you see where people try to be more, not pro Soviet, but more deferential to the Soviet Union than others. A very good example of this, of how this worked and this may be a bad example, but it comes to mind, is how people are bending over backwards now to kiss Donald Trump's butt.

Everybody is, Bezos is giving a million for his inauguration, everybody is bending over, Christopher Wray has resigned, everybody's bending over backwards. And the thing is that none of

that on a certain level needs to be done. But everybody wants to maximize favor. Jeff Bezos thinks that if I don't, if I don't grease Trump's palms now a competitor might do it more and then I get left out of it.

And so what it was, people were domestically currying favor from the Soviet Union for things that the Soviet Union wasn't demanding or asking. And people would debase themselves in the face of Soviet power domestically. And your relationship with the Soviet Union, how you acted toward the Soviet Union became a political hard currency in Finnish domestic politics, and sauna evenings, how many times you were invited to a sauna evening at the Soviet embassy became a measure of how good you were as a politician. A very important measure, not the only, but a very important measure becomes by the 70s is how good are you in with the with the Soviet Union, and as I said, for things that not the Soviet Union weren't asking for, there's a lot of self censorship in the media.

One example of this is I mentioned brief very briefly in my book, in really up until the 1970s, you could read in Finland, in Finnish translation, books that were published in the West that were critical of the Soviet Union or that critically looked at Soviet foreign policy or domestic policy, the Finnish media would often mention very openly, talk very openly about political dissidents in the Soviet Union. This begins to change in the 70s when Aleksandr Solzhenitsyn's book, *The Gulag Archipelago*, comes out and Solzhenitsyn is a well known dissident in the Soviet Union and the, there's discussion and there's an attempt by one Finnish publisher to publish the book in Finnish. The pressure inside the company, I believe it was either Ohtava or Tommi, one of the two big publishing houses at the time, the pressure inside that publishing house, but also from other politicians who were close to the company, not to publish it became so strong that they refused to publish it. The Soviet union didn't demand that the *Gulag Archipelago* not be published and finished. They made no request of any kind for that. If it had been published, and the thing was that the book is not published in Finnish in Finland, but it's published in Finnish by a publishing house in Sweden and then brought to Finland to be sold. And the Soviets didn't complain about that either, but it becomes a political culture in which, you're measured by how much you bow to Soviet power, but it has no, in a lot of respects, no real connection to what that power wants. It just becomes a game

among Finns over this. Now there are cases in which, the Soviets do criticize things that happen in Finland or some things that get published and so forth. But, ultimately the consequences aren't great.

The foreign policy is very realistic. And I think that, and it's one that created a lot of benefits for Finland, but it was how the question of Soviet power was used domestically. And that was stuff that Finns allowed to happen. And then the other level is in terms of realism and foreign policy, countries that neighbor each other tend to want to avoid conflict with those countries. A lot of what, Finland did in terms of cultivating good relations with the Soviet Union would have happened if the Soviet Union was a Swiss style democracy that minded its own business. There are countries, the United States is deferential to because it doesn't want to offend it. It's not just small powers that do this large powers do it as well. So I think that needs to be considered as well, is that there's just some of this, in terms of the foreign policy, the relationship between the governments and so forth, that some of this is just normal. Avoid torquing your neighbor off too much.

Nguyen: Yeah, no, I've definitely read about this in David Arter's article about post-Finlandization. I think he describes exactly what you're saying is that it went to a point where the domestic effects were more than what was demanded by the Soviet Union. So yeah, that definitely makes sense. In your opinion, why did this culture develop? Was it just perceived fears that grew over time? Was it because something about Kekkonen and his rule or what about this caused this to happen?

Lavery: That's a good question. And I think part of it is, I just think it's a culture of opportunism and also that the Soviets made it clear. In terms of meddling in Finnish domestic affairs, they did make it very clear whom they liked and whom they didn't like. So if you're a politician in, 1960s Finland, it's clear you don't want to be on Moscow's blacklist. And part of this is just there were benefits of being on Moscow's good side.

You could, go to the Soviet embassy for sauna nights. The Soviets didn't really give money to Finnish political parties or anything. There's some financial interactions between the Soviet Union, the Finnish Communist Party, but so it was mostly just status and small, kind of, benefits economically, but I think the problem is that it was a culture of opportunism. People saw that the

only way you get forward in politics is by openly backing the foreign policy.

It does also have to go with Kekkonen in the sense that Kekkonen, unlike Paasikivi, had to, even though you think about a guy who was president for 26 years, he must have had it pretty easy as president in terms of exercising power. That actually doesn't occur until the 1970s. Because, when he becomes president in 1956 by one electoral vote, Finland had an electoral college at that time, and he wins by one electoral vote, 150 to 149. In 1962, at one point, there's an opposition candidate who, according to polls, would have beaten him. And then in 1968, he wins pretty handily, but there were opposition parties. Kekkonen didn't command the personal respect, the only way Kekkonen ultimately could get people to follow him was by playing the Moscow card. "I'm the only guy who can maintain good relations with the Soviet Union." The Soviets would say Kekkonen is our man. And if you're a politician in another party or even in Kekkonen's old party the Agrarian League slash Centre party, how do you move ahead? You move ahead by by pleasing the president.

So Kekkonen really emphasizes this more because he doesn't have really any other levers that he can use over, as a politician, over the population. Paasikivi was much different. When he becomes prime minister, he becomes prime minister in part 1944 because of his knowledge of the Soviet Union and his diplomacy with the Soviet Union over the decades, but also he was a guy who was just widely respected. He wasn't the most loving, most warm politician or anything, but people respected him outside of his own political party. Outside of his own movement. This is a guy who stood up to fascists in the early 1930s, when he took over leadership of Finland's National Coalition Party, Finland's main center right party. He had been involved in so many political crises and conflicts over his career. People really trusted him. People didn't trust Kekkonen. And when Kekkonen ran for president in 1956, you can look this up, he won by only one vote because and it took several rounds of voting.

He was seen as a man of loose morals. The Boulevard Papers, Kekkonen, drunk in a hotel, Kekkonen visits bordello's, Kekkonen this. . . So people didn't trust him either as a politician or a human being. With Paasikivi people trusted him even if they didn't like his foreign policy. People would back him even if they didn't like his foreign policy because he was Paasikivi. Paasikivi also,

if you read his diaries, he had people frequently over who totally disagreed with his management of Finnish-Soviet relations. And he talked and he'd have him back a few months later. He was a much more confident politician and he had more of the country behind him. Because of his experiences, people learned he wasn't trusted before he became president with many difficult tasks. Kekkonen didn't have that. Kekkonen had to build his power base as president by holding onto relations with Moscow. And then as he becomes more entrenched in the job, you please Kekkonen by pleasing the Soviets and vice versa. And it's just a lot of opportunism in the way.

So by the end of the seventies, all the political parties, with the exception of a handful of small ones, the four major political parties in the country all considered themselves Kekkonen parties. So they backed the president, and Russia backed Paasikivi. They made it very clear. In 1940, when the president of Finland dies in office and there's a new election, Russia makes it very, it's always made very clear they want Paasikivi president. Paasikivi he, my sense of him was that he realized this is dealing with the Soviets, we have to deal with it. And, it's the old saying, this is a dirty job, but somebody has to do it. Kekkonen didn't see it as a dirty job. He saw it as a way of staying in office. Possibly when he took office, he was in his 70s already. Also he had more of this, you know, if you guys don't like it, you know, meaning the voters, if you guys don't like this, just kiss my butt, I'm going to go play with my grandchildren after this. So he didn't need, you gotta want the job to, to get those positions. You gotta want it. I'm not saying you didn't have any ambition, he did, but it wasn't as, as overweening and he came from a much different body of experiences than did Kekkonen.

Nguyen: We talked about this a little bit earlier about how Sweden, and along with other countries, their situations are different than Finland. But I think a lot of people, when they think of the Nordics and Cold War era politics that they often clump Sweden and Finland together. I guess, could you talk a little bit about what set Sweden aside from Finland, what made it different was their relationship with neutrality? You mentioned the border, traditions, history, what about it made it different?

Lavery: I think there's a few differences. And it plays out when you get to the two countries joining NATO, and that is that for Finland neutrality pretty much came out of, Finland had considered

itself neutral in the twenties and thirties, but it didn't last long enough to really get any traction.

Sweden has been neutral basically before it joined NATO, it had been neutral since 1815. And so its neutrality over those centuries, the neutrality develops into something that "we're neutral in respect to all conflicts." Because over this decade's generation, sometimes the threat was Germany, sometimes it was Russia, sometimes it was Britain, sometimes it was nobody. So Sweden's neutrality wasn't targeted toward anybody.

The Finnish brand of neutrality, the touch point of it was the Soviet Union, that we are neutral in a way that does not offend the Soviet Union. We can sometimes offend the West. We don't want to, we want the world to think that we are neutral, but it was neutral in terms of not offending the Soviets. And that's the big difference. Also, if you look at the Cold War era, Sweden's neutrality had developed various escape hatches to NATO in the Cold War. As I said, Sweden developed a nuclear weapon. And that idea with the nuclear bomb was a way of defending Swedish neutrality. This is another thing too, is that Sweden spent a lot more money on it's military establishment in the Cold War era and actually in the 20s and 30s as well. They make their own fighter aircraft, there's Bofors, the artillery company. There's a whole military industrial complex in Sweden that, for the size of the country, probably no other country in the world has. And so there's more of an investment in the military and the idea that if you have a strong military, you can create a deterrence from foreign threats.

Nguyen: Final question for this section; when did Finlandization end?

Lavery: A good question. And give me a second to think about that. Yeah, that's a good question. I think if you look at Finlandization as interstate relations. As I said, I look at Finlandization, there's Finnish-Soviet interstate relations, then there's this domestic politicking that goes on. Both of them, the beginning of the end is when Gorbachev becomes leader of the Soviet Union. That becomes the big turning point because Gorbachev, he becomes leader in 1985. In 1989, he formally calls Finland a neutral country, which, Soviet leaders had refused to use the N word. Because if you, for them, neutral meant essentially you were a part of the West. And also, Finland realized also that it needed to realign its relations with Western Europe because this is the time of Western European

integration that's going on. And you begin to see the Soviet Union disintegrating or the Soviet grip on Eastern Europe disintegrating.

So this nice, comfortable position Finland had made for itself that I talked about earlier, you have Western European integrating, Eastern Europe disintegrating, Finland could find itself a part of neither and impacted negatively by both. The idea of having a neutral, having a different kind of foreign policy that wasn't so deferential to the Soviet Union starts at that time. It's something that at the time things are being said, but it's still a strong sense really throughout the 80s that the relationship is pretty much unchanged. But people are discussing it.

I remember in 1988 when there was a presidential election that Max Jakobson, a guy whose name you've probably encountered who was a major writer on Finnish foreign policy in the Cold War era, he writes in 1989 in an article I read that this will be the last presidential election that we'll use the term Paasikivi Kekkonen line, as in the name of the first country's official foreign policy. And I remember reading that thinking, "wow," people were saying that's quite a statement, but it's true. In the election in 1994, everything had changed in six years so much. And then Finland, after the collapse of the Soviet Union begins to cultivate relations with NATO, becomes a member of the European Union, and so you're no longer a purely neutral country anymore.

So I, that's where I think as a foreign policy, it starts, but now, what doesn't change is the idea in Finland that there's still a strong sense in Finnish foreign policy up until the war in Ukraine that, you know, of not, we've talked about this before, not joining NATO as there still is this understanding that the Soviets have a defensive interest or the Russians have a defensive interest in Finland and Finland, as long as Finland does not involve itself in alliances or organizations that are directly targeted against Russia, Russia will leave Finland alone. So that part of the kind of, if you talk about the intellectual or the ideological underpinnings of Finland's foreign policy, Finlandization from the Cold War period, that still sticks around this idea that, we shouldn't do anything that affects their defensive interests and also from the Cold War period, the idea that Russia can be an economic opportunity for Finland begins.

Finnish businesses are heavily in there in the nineties when, as I said last time, we didn't know

in the early nineties, what kind of country Russia was going to become. There were a lot of, a lot of signs that Russia was going to become a democracy, with a functioning market economy and, little corruption and all of this. As I said last time the idea that people have now that we should, we were too naïve as far as Russia was concerned, I think in some isolated instances, that's true, but we fought the Cold War. We wanted to see the end of communism and that you're going to turn around in 1991 with the Soviet Union collapsing saying we don't want to have anything to do with that. We're going to get prepared for the next round of conflict because we know 10 years down the road there's going to be this guy Putin. You don't know that. But that's how it ends.

You might want to say where does the point where kind of all of the intellectual underpinnings and assumptions of Finland's Cold War foreign policy really come to an end? It's with the invasion of Ukraine, because no one says now in Finland that the the Russians have only a defensive interest in Finland. I think that's true still, but nobody says that. So those underpinnings are all gone. Yeah, in that sense, you have it until, I think in terms of the domestic aspect of it, in terms of currying Russian favor in order to advance politically, domestically that, that was gone even, you could even say by, the last couple of years of the Soviet Union that there became more open criticism of the Soviet Union. After the end of the Soviet Union, Russia was handled and the media, and by politicians, as they would criticize any country. But then again, you have to look at it that, for certain politicians, people look, for example, now at the presidency of Tarja Halonen and that she was very nice to Putin. And Niinistö still was too, but you have to separate, is that just trying to have the best relationship you can with a very large neighbor or is it just being supine?

So there are those things as well. But I think that, in terms of the domestic dimension of it, that was gone in a lot of respects even before the Soviet Union ended. Nobody since the 90s sought to develop a political base by currying favor with the Russians and in a lot of cases, it was the direct opposite. So that's where I would see the end of those, if you want to look at it as two tracks.

I think in Finland there was always, and this is something that I think a lot of Finnish commentators don't often get is that, I think there was a sense in Finland that there are, what the Soviet Union did was, I'll give you another example. Helmut Schmidt, the former the chancellor of West Germany in

the 1970s and eighties, once said that, 90 percent of what Russia does is Russian and 10 percent of what it does is Communist. That is that, if you look at kind of the sweep of Russian history, attempts to expand power, certain things, and I think for Finns, there was an understanding that there are certain things even after with the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia is still going to be a great power in the world. Now, it might be a less threatening great power to Finland. It might be a country that becomes more democratic and open, but, it's still going to be a big power. It's still going to have security interests. That will put it in conflict with other countries. And I don't think, there was never that level of wishful thinking, magical thinking in Finland.

I think that there was a fairly good understanding that this was, and this is part of the reason why Finland does make these, collaborative efforts with NATO in the 1990s is that, they realized that, and Paasikivi said this, was that, Russia might not always be a great power in the world, but it will always be one to us. And Finns, even in the nineties, went a step more. They realized that, with the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia will still be a major player in the world. It might be down now. It might not ever be as menacing or as aggressive as the Soviet Union was, but it's still going to be a very, a big major power.

So there was a sense there that there is a, and this also comes out I think a lot in the discourse in the early two thousands, when it's clear that Vladimir Putin is not interested in developing democracy in Russia, that in fact, a lot of Finnish commentators, were fairly quick to watch quicker than in the U. S. or I see in Germany or in other countries to notice this that Putin was not interested in setting up a democracy like we know it. And it was, I think it's a lot of that was, in Finland that was accepted. You know, it's okay, the Russians have this long tradition with authoritarian government, of course, this is Russia.

Nguyen: So we've talked about how the foreign policy Finland says they shouldn't do anything to endanger this defensive interest that Russia has in Finland. But if we look at their actual actions when they joined the EU, and then they started participating in NATO and the Partnership for Peace, and then If we look at the national security documents, they slowly mention non-alignment and military non-alignment less and less. And then I think it's 2013, something, 2013, 2014, they say

“We’re keeping our options open for a military alliance.” So how does that align with this idea that Finlandization did not end until actual NATO accession?

Lavery: What I meant was that the, if you want to look at kind of the total end of Finlandization as this Cold War foreign policy, it’s the invasion of Ukraine because you still have some of the assumptions and underpinnings, as I talked about, Russia has a defensive interest in Finland. So that’s why, but on the other hand, especially as you get into Putin’s wars in Georgia and other places, and the Russians and the media start talking about, the near abroad as a sphere of influence, this is not contradictory. There’s a long history of this, this is what Finland does. I talked about World War Two and how, Finland was fighting on the side of Germany while it was looking for a peaceful solution with the Soviet Union in the back, this is another replay of that, that yes, there’s the official foreign policy, there’s the way that government and the people would like things to go, but, an understanding that there also needs to be a plan B, if it can be found. So yeah you’re keeping your assumptions about Russia up, in terms of its defensive interest in Finland, also, that Russia might become a democracy, Russia might become this, but at the same time, you want to have that option. People talked about the NATO option starting in the early 2000s, as you mentioned, but essentially the NATO option was there already, when the Soviet Union collapsed and NATO started these various collaborative efforts, with non NATO countries, and then enlarged into Eastern Europe and so forth. This is not contradictory in that sense of Finland’s foreign policy. You want to have the back door to to that. So what I meant by the end of Finlandization was the end of a lot of these widespread assumptions about Russia that underpinned the foreign policy.

That’s when that ends. Most of it’s over, though, by the collapse of the Soviet Union. But as I said, some of these things about Russia defensive interests and also the historical experience that nobody was going to help, nobody helped Finland via the Soviet Union. People talk about “Why didn’t Finland join?” Nobody wanted to join, because for a lot of reasons. Finns could look back at, the one time Finland had a military agreement, it wasn’t a formal military alliance, but a military collaboration with a country, it didn’t go too well, and attempts to create alliances in the 20s and 30s went nowhere. So it’s like you have a country that has 80 years of, when the Cold War ends, some

70, 80 years of taking care of its own security policy, its own foreign affairs and it's been successful. The country's remained independent, the country became more prosperous, and so forth.

You quickly walk away from that and in the embrace of an alliance system when you don't have a great experience with alliances? No, it takes a while. And also, and I think I mentioned something last time, and I think it's very much forgotten and "Why didn't we join NATO earlier?" You know, In the nineties, there was a big discussion as to, what NATO should become. So Finland was looking in countries that were not NATO members. We're looking at an alliance that had lost its reason for existence. The Soviet Union was gone. It didn't look like Russia was going to be much of a threat in any way in the foreseeable future. NATO didn't know what its mission was and it becomes more complicated when you go to the war in the former Yugoslavia where NATO is involved, but none of that territory in former Yugoslavia is a part of NATO. And then you have the war in Afghanistan and Iraq. Is NATO going to be, and this was a concern in Finland, is NATO going to be some world policeman or some, not a defensive alliance, but some kind of arm of American expansion or projection of American power rather than a defensive alliance for European countries and countries in the North Atlantic area, especially around the Iraq war when that goes on. There's a lot of things that kind of looking at Finland's relationship with NATO from the end of the Cold War until it joined NATO that are forgotten in all of this. Things that happened and concerning NATO, concerning the United States and various assumptions about that. And also just the Finn's historical experiences with alliances and with military conflict.

Nguyen: Yeah, that totally makes sense. During this period after the Cold War, I know we talked a little bit about this idea of appeasement versus constitutionalism. Was this debate still going on internally at this time, this idea that Finnish politicians are unsure about what to do, that they're still arguing for either side or was the debate different?

Lavery: People didn't call it constitutionalism versus appeasement. What happens is after the Cold War the appeasement idea goes away and there's maybe a light constitutionalism in the sense that Finland joins these various collaborations with NATO. Finland begins to expect Russia to adhere to norms of democracy and rule of law and so forth. And this is why Finland joins the

European union is that, one of the reasons, is that there's not really a, the EU is not an alliance, but there was real concern about, in the early nineties, Russia was a pretty chaotic place. Would Finland have to deal with in the near future, not a military aggressive Russia, stalin, rolling over Eastern Europe, but would it just be so chaotic that if there'd be civil war in Russia, who would take over? There was no predictability. And so, there too, there's a sense of kind of the constitutionalist, let's make agreements, let's hold the Russians to them, and let's not be as flexible as we might be on certain things. But it is a light form of constitutionalism.

And because the Russians aren't doing specifically anything threatening vis-à-vis Finland, it's just the situation in Russia. So they don't call it constitutionalism versus appeasement, but a lot of the words and concepts are there, as I just mentioned about, Finland's defensive importance to [Russia] and stuff like that. But it leans more toward constitutionalism and as time goes on, that becomes harder, the Finnish positions harden on that. And I think that's a role of Finland becoming more more integrated member of the European Union and then also these collaborations with NATO are well established and so forth.

Nguyen: Yeah, so this light constitutionalism, as you call it, is what is predominant after the end of the Cold War, but there's still this sense of Russia is a great power. A need to be a little bit cautious still. Is that a separate sentiment or is it integrated within it?

Lavery: I think it's all one in the same thing, and I think this is why it's difficult for people when they look back on the period from the end of the Soviet Union until I would say really through the Russian takeover of Crimea in 2014, that period that there are elements of both of those traditions in Finland's foreign policy, it tends more toward, you need to really choose one or the other, it's more constitutionalist than constructive appeasement. But there's elements of both and it's not because of, as I said, it's not so much of, some of this has to do with ambivalence about Russia. But some of it also has to do with ambivalence about NATO and the West, as I just mentioned. And in this history of a lack of help from the outside world, president Niinistö mentioned this early in his presidency, but also when he was involved in other positions before he became president and that, before the invasion of Ukraine and before Russia took all these, and this is actually still true, that

half of Russia's border with NATO, if Finland joined NATO, half of Finland's border with NATO would be the Finnish Russian border, because all you have is that little part of Northern Norway and then the Baltic States. And then yeah, that would be it. Is NATO prepared to defend that kind of, distant corner of northeastern Europe? Which is a legitimate question, is that all of a sudden Finland would end up having to take this massive responsibility is being a frontline state for Russia.

And a lot of people said "We got to think about that," and that's what led a lot of people to think, okay, let's just stick with the, and the foreign policy had been practiced since the early nineties, this idea of military non-alignment, or we're going to keep the NATO option open didn't really damage Finland's position in Europe. It wasn't like, the country became a pariah or the country became less secure. It became more secure. And then when people felt that it, 2022, when that foreign policy had reached the end of the road, just like people felt in the late 80s and early 90s, that the previous foreign policy reached the end of the road, people changed it and Finland had been building these back channels with NATO and other countries that made them joining, easy and so forth.

I wouldn't be surprised now if there was somewhere in the depths of the Finnish foreign ministry, people developing plans on what happens if Putin wins in Ukraine, what happens if he loses? What's the next, what's the next step you have to anticipate? What's the next backdoor we need to build?

Nguyen: I think we alluded you alluded to this a little bit earlier when you mentioned how this light constitutionalism got stronger over time. And I mentioned Finland wanted to increase its integration and it changed its doctrine to not mention military non-alliance as much and opened up this option, that as you said was already available at the beginning. Do you think that this change over time of Finland's security options opening up and being more receptive to military cooperation is that part of just integration to the West in general is that or is that a trend caused by something else?

Lavery: It's mostly just, yeah, it's an integration with the West and greater comfort with it, but also, the fact that Russia has become much more menacing, I think both contribute to it.

Nguyen: And then moving on to the last section, we talked about this a little bit earlier about other countries being used as examples when they shouldn't be. What do you think about the use of

Finlandization in other contexts like in Taiwan or Ukraine, where officials say oh, “they should take the Finnish model”?

Lavery: I actually did an interview with a journalist with this about, it was right after the takeover of Crimea. I think that they I’ll just say that part of it is, this is something that separates historians from political scientists and international relations scholars, is that as historians, we’re reluctant to say the case of one country or community, you can take that as a model and cross time and space and apply it to another place. And so that’s the, I’ll just say that’s the one bias that I come from, but I think in the case of Ukraine, the problem goes back to what I said, that Russia was willing to accept the relationship with Finland that was short of Soviet conquest of Finland, so it takes both sides to agree to this.

Russia has given no signal that it is willing to have such an arrangement with Ukraine, where Ukraine would be free, it’d be democratic, it would, have its open society, but it would defer to Russian interests in foreign policy and would have a government that would seek to be as friendly with Russia as possible.

Putin won’t settle for that. There’s nothing in that sense, I think the model is moot. Also just the immorality of asking a country that is still fighting in the field to accept such a solution. Finland accepted the relationship with the Soviet Union when it lost, when it had to surrender, when it had fought a war, it had done its best, it kept the Soviets out of the country, but it couldn’t keep them out forever, so they cut a deal. Ukraine is not in that position yet. A peaceful solution work. It would also, I think, lead to a situation where it would create a great deal of chaos in Ukraine.

I don’t see any consensus in Ukraine for such a solution in Finland in 1944. There was, as I said, there was the idea that, okay, this is the only way we can go. I think if Zelenskyy decided tomorrow that, okay, we’re going to give up some of the Donbass, and then we’re going to, see if we can create this great relationship with Putin he’d be out of office.

And as I said, then you go back to Putin probably doesn’t want the solution anyway because Russia’s interest in Ukraine is not defensive. It’s to project more power over the long haul. I think the same thing goes with Taiwan. The Chinese are trying to expand in the Pacific Ocean. They’re

building islands, and their interest in Taiwan is part of that larger expansion of power. And the thing is that, we know that China doesn't have a defensive interest in Taiwan because, up until, the 1970s, there were American troops in Taiwan, and it still didn't really bother the Chinese.

Taiwan has all kinds of relationships with the world that China doesn't like, but it's not going to do anything about it, even though it could. And again, that's not something, a solution that I think the government in Beijing would accept. And then again, the moral question of you're asking a country that has been fighting this good fight in Taiwan since 1949, you're just going to ask them to, surrender.

There might come a time when Taiwan feels like that, but that would have to be, and again, if you had a government come to power in Taiwan that wanted a, quote unquote, Finland solution to everything, it'd be out of office in days. There's no consensus for it. You have to have that, especially when you're dealing with countries like, and I think this is some, one of the lessons of that, that I have learned big lessons about looking at Finland's foreign policy since independence is that, but you see it in Finland, you see it in Ukraine and you see it in Taiwan, that, ultimately in a democracy, a foreign policy doesn't work if the people don't want it. In 1944 in Finland, people were prepared for a Finland solution to Finnish-Soviet relations, and that's partially why it worked, people in Ukraine and Taiwan are not ready for that, the people don't want it.

You can ask another question whether maybe the people should want it, but that doesn't, but you also see in terms of Finland. The Finns didn't want to be a part of NATO, overwhelmingly didn't wanna be a part of NATO until they wanted to. Why I find the question interesting because it does, even though I said I don't like models being spread over time and space, what I do think the three cases do show is that, to have this kind of a solution where a smaller power is very differential to its larger neighbor, you have to have the larger neighbor agree to it in one way or another, and it has to enjoy the backing of the people in the smaller country, assuming that smaller country's a democracy. And in Finland in 1944, you had both come together. Neither of these are coming together in the other two cases. In that sense, if you look at the questions of democracy and the aims of the larger power, they do come together, but there, it just shows that the model cannot just be applied. You

have to have certain, and this is something that political scientists and IR scholars do, you have to have a certain set of criteria that have to be met in order to have that situation occur. And neither one of them occurs in Ukraine or Taiwan.

Nguyen: And is there anything else that we can learn from Finland's experience and Finlandization about small state relations, or is that the lesson, that both states need to agree and the people need to agree?

Lavery: I think that's part of it. I also think it's the danger of the small state that the relation with the larger power can really overwhelm domestic politics if people in that country allow it to be done.

Nguyen: Okay, and then the very last question, I forgot to go over this a while ago. During the Cold War, how important was the *YYA-sopimus*?

Lavery: It was incredibly important. It was seen as the, the 10 commandments of Finnish-Soviet relations, the touchstone, and every time Finnish and Soviet leaders would meet, they would refer to it.

Just on a personal level to show how Finnish-Soviet relations really permeated, even on the local level, in the spring of 1983 in April, 1983, the YYA Treaty, as it's called in Finnish, or the FCMA Treaty, Treaty of Friendship Cooperation and Mutual Assistance. The treaty turned 35 years old. It had its 35th anniversary in April 1983. I was an exchange student in Finland in high school. And I lived in a town in northern Finland of about 10,000 people. And to celebrate the anniversary, there was, set up by, it's a joint Finnish-Soviet effort. There was a thing called the Friendship Train, and it was a train that went from town to town throughout Finland and there was a Soviet delegation on there, but there were also Finnish politicians and people from industry and business who traveled and would visit places in these towns to have a celebration or something to do with the YYA Treaty.

In the school I was in I studied I studied Russian. And when the train stopped in our town there were like the mayor of the town came to the train station, brought the delegate, all this folderol, but a Russian teacher, a woman who taught Russian in the Soviet Union came to our Russian class and we got to ask her questions about the Soviet Union and so forth, so that's how it was. So it had become so much a part of the Finnish-Soviet relationship that even in a small town in, you know, northern

Finland, there were official celebrations for it.

No, it was very important. And for the Finnish side, it was a treaty that Finland would show to the West, is this is a sign that we're not a part of the Soviet sphere of influence, we're an independent country because in the treaty, Soviets say it. On the other hand, for the Soviets, it was, we now know from archives and other things, it was the functional equivalent of a military alliance.

The Soviets had everything they needed, they felt, in order to, in the event of a war, either take over Finland or use Finnish resources, or have the Finns oppose some opponent of the Soviet Union. So no, it was a very, holy document.

Nguyen: That's all the questions that I had. Thank you so much for your time.

Lavery: Of course, reach out to me again later if you want to talk some more.

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